

Assessment of Islamic (Interest Free Banking) Prospects, Opportunity and Challenges in Ethiopia In The Case Of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, West Addis District

Abdlmegid Awel Chali

A GradXs Researcher enrolled in PhD program from Livingstone International University of Tourism Excellence and Business Management (LIUTEBM), Zambia Lusaka

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Abstract

This study presents new evidence on awareness, prospects, challenges and opportunities of Islamic banking in Ethiopia that are actually consistent with what Islamic Banking literature has revealed about the operations of Islamic banking elsewhere. To do so, descriptive research design of cross-sectional survey method which is be observational in its nature is used to realize the objectives of the study.

To be specific, the analysis suggests that there is low level of awareness about the operations of Islamic banking while respondents with different background has shown statistically significant variance in terms of awareness, and widely held long standing about Islamic banking operations. In addition, respondent's prospects assessment score with regard to the operations of Islamic banking is high and higher than average expected score while respondents with different background has shown significant variance in terms of their assessment. Moreover, lack of awareness, regulatory and supervisory challenges, institutional challenges, lack of support and link institutions, gap in research and development in Islamic studies as, lack of qualified human resource as well as wrongful association with specific religion and the global terrorism movements in recent times has been reported as one of the major problems facing Islamic banking in Ethiopia. In Ethiopian there is potential customer and Ethiopian Investment framework is favorable also for investors, so this creates favorable condition for the development of IFB. On the other side, the challenges to deliver IFB services as: lack of Sharia advisor, lack of supportive regulatory directives, lack of awareness of customer about IFB products and absence of equity markets. On the other hand, unavailability of IFB service in all branches, unequal treatment of debt and equity and double taxation and lack of trust with in the bank are the main challenges customer face to utilize the products. Accordingly, the following recommendations were forwarded by the researcher based on the results of the findings in conjunction with literature review reflections: aggressive promotion and marketing campaign about IFB products, provide sustainable and continuous training to build the capacity of the manpower, the bank shall increase accessibility of its products with in all branches, the bank has to have Sharia advisor, the bank should give the required attention and focus for the business and the bank has to be transparent in its IFB business undertaking, in addition government should prepare compatible regulatory framework.

Key Words: Islamic banking, awareness, prospects, challenges, Riba, Interest Free Bank

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ACRONYMS

NBE	NATIONAL BANK OF ETHIOPIA
CBE	COMMERCIAL BANK OF ETHIOPIA
ISB	ISLAMIC BANKING
IFB	INTEREST FREE BANKING
BOA	BANK OF ABYSSINIYA
COB	COOPERATIVE BANK OF OROMIA
NIB	INTERNATIONAL BANK,
IF IFSIs	ISLAMIC FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS
PBUOH	PEACE BE UP ON HIM
ICCS	ISLAMIC CROSS CURRENCIES SWAP
WDIBF	WORLD DATABASE FOR ISLAMIC BANKING AND FINANCE
ECX	ETHIOPIA COMMODITY EXCHANGE

CHAPTER ONE

1. INTRODUCTION

Islamic finance is a phenomenon that is increasingly recognized on the world's financial markets. It is originating in the Middle East where today the growth rates of Islamic financing assets are exceeding those of conventional banking assets (e.g. in Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, Kuwait and Qatar). In 2014, the assets of Islamic banks grew by 34% in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries (EY, 2015). As a result, Islamic finance is now systemically important in the Middle East but also in Asia and the rest of the world (IMF, 2017). In 2015, total worldwide Islamic financial services comprised \$1.88 trillion of which \$1.497 trillion are Islamic banking assets (IFSB, 2016).

Recently, Saudi Arabia drew the attention of global investors when it announced the issuance of Islamic bonds ('sukuk'), amounting to \$9 billion. According to the Ministry of Finance, investors placed bids of more than \$33 billion attesting a grand interest in Islamic financing products not only stemming from the Middle East (Narayanan & Sharif, 2017). Financing in accordance with the Sharia is also spreading to non-Muslim countries. For example the London stocks exchange

designed different indices that cover Islamic financing activities. Especially in the light of the devastating consequences of the subprime mortgage crisis in 2007 in the USA and its development to a global financial crisis which was caused and fuelled by speculative transactions, exorbitant gearing as well as a large gap between savings and expenditure in the USA. Islamic financing is considered as an arising alternative because these procedures are forbidden in Islamic banking (McKibbin&Stoeckel, 2010; Saeed&Izzeldin, in press).

Islamic banks differ from conventional banks as they face a couple of prohibitions imposed by the Sharia. They do not pay or receive interest since it is not allowed to generate money with money (Al-Hares, AbuGhazaleh, & El-Galfy, 2013). Further, they must not transact business with customers that earn money with products which are forbidden in the Islam, e.g. gambling, pork or alcohol. As mentioned before, excessive risk, uncertainty or exploitation is not permitted (El Hawary, Grais, & Iqbal, 2004; Khediri, Charfeddine, & Youssef, 2015). Risk is further dispersed by the principle of profit and loss sharing according to which both customer and bank bear potential gains or losses.

This shall prevent making advantage of the other party and recklessness in managing the funds (El Hawary et al., 2004; Khediri et al., 2015). Islamic banks claim this principle as one of their key advantages, however, it is often criticized that Islamic banking does not differ from conventional banking and is not more ethical or religious (Khan, 2010). Some even argue that Muslims are exploited by Islamic banks (Khediri et al., 2015). The focus of this research is different. It examines financial reasons to choose or avoid an Islamic bank, for instance the solvency and liquidity of banks that convey security. As Islamic banking became more prominent in recent years, it is an increasingly researched topic. Nevertheless, the extent of academic literature on Islamic finance is still comparatively small (Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt, & Merrouche, 2013).

Islamic banking and finance system distinguish from the conventional financial system is based on a comprehensive system of ethics and moral values stemming from the Islamic religion. Unlike conventional finance, Islamic finance is founded on overarching principles that constitute the guidelines governing any Islamic economic or financial dealings (Omar.M 2013).

Islamic banking is a banking system that is consistent with the Sharia (Islamic law) and as such, an important part of the system is the prohibition on collecting *riba* (interest or usury). The Sharia also prohibits trading in financial risk because this is seen as a form of gambling something forbidden in Islam. Another prohibition under the Sharia is that Muslims cannot invest in businesses that are considered *haram* (forbidden or sinful) such as those that sell alcohol, pork, engage in gambling or produce un-Islamic media. (Altiby 2010). As of 2014, Sharia-compliant financial institutions represented approximately 1% of total world assets. By 2009 there were over 300 banks and 250 mutual funds around the world complying with Islamic principles and as of 2014 total assets of around 2\$ trillion were Sharia-compliant.

According to Ernst & Young, although Islamic banking still makes up only a fraction of the banking system of Muslims, it has been growing faster than banking assets as a whole, growing at an annual rate of 17.6% between 2009 and 2013, and is projected to grow by an average of

19.7% a year to 2018. The first organized Islamic financial institution is Baitul Mal, which translates to “House of Money” and was established in the early days of Islam.

Originally, administration of taxes, distribution of zakat (wealth tax), and managing government expenditures were the main function of BaitulMal. During the time of the Prophet Mohammed (pbuh) and Abu Bakr Al Sidiq, the first of the Rashidun caliphate, all revenues received were distributed.

Immediately; therefore, there was no need for a permanent Baitul Mal. The actual establishment of BaitulMal as an organized financial institution is attributed to Omar Bin Al Khatab, the second caliph. During this period there was a large increase in state revenue from the concord territories that needed to be managed. A central treasury was established in Medina, headed by Abdulla bin Arqam as treasury officer, and provincial treasuries were also set to manage the province revenues and expenditure and to remit the net proceeds to the central treasury. For bookkeeping and accounting, a separate accounts department was established. The major sources of funding for Baitul Mal were revenues from concord territories, zakat (wealth tax applied at the rate of 2.5 percent on all Muslims), jizia (tax due from non-Muslims for providing protection), and kharaj (land tax). Secondary sources of funding included sadaqah (donations) and any funds or properties with no owners or legal heirs. On the expenditure side, and apart from the state expenses such as payment of salaries and other expenditures, Omar Bin Al Khatab introduced the first of what we now call Social Security. This included providing income to the poor, elderly, orphaned, widowed, and disabled, as well as unemployment insurance, retirement pensions, and public trusteeship. During this time, allowance to non-Muslims and relief from jizia were also first applied. During the early days of Islam, some banking activities took place in the form of custody of money and precious items and remittances. As mentioned by Haron and Shanmugam (1997), AzZubair ben AlAwwam was the first person to apply the Islamic principle of qard, or loan in the history of Islamic banking.

Currently the Ethiopian government gives, a permission to setup Islamic (interest free banking system). This is breakthrough for the Muslim community. Therefore, Ethiopia is a country which is a favorable condition for the growth of Islamic banking. Moreover, this research paper tries to address the potentiality of Islamic banking model, whether Ethiopian Muslims have a genuine need for Islamic banking and whether there is a gap in addressing this basic, societal as well as economic need.

1.1. Background of the study

One of the main issues that concerned Muslim scholars was how to eliminate riba from their lives and how they could make their financial dealings compliant with their Sharia. Rashid Rida (1865–1935) was a Syrian scholar and jurist who joined Jamal AID in Al Afghani (1838–1897) and Mohamed Abdu (1849–1905) in their news paper Al-Urwa al-Wuthqa and the later launched Al Manar weekly news paper in Cairo, where they published articles that discussed the legitimacy of interest. This period has also witnessed thinkers such as Hassan AlBanna (1906–1949), the founder of the Muslim Brotherhood (the foremost of Egypt’s resurgent Islamic Organization), Sayed Qutb (1906–1966) one of the foremost figures in modern Sunni Islamic revivalism and the thinker of the Muslim Brotherhood in Egypt, and Syed Abul Ala Mawdudi (1903–1979), a Sunni Pakistani journalist, the founder of Islamic revivalist party

Jamaat-e-Islam and a major Islamic thinker and revivalist leader. Their ideas and writings on how to reestablish the Islamic state and how to reinforce Islamic Sharia in to all aspects of Muslims lives, have helped in enhancing the awareness of the importance of establishing the Islamic financial system in Muslims' minds. Islamic banking, as an institution, has only been around for almost 70 years, whereas the idea of interest-free banking has been around for as long as the inception of Islam. The first attempt to establish an interest free bank, which ended unsuccessfully, was in the mid-1940s in Malaysia. The idea was to invest pilgrims' savings in real estate and plantations in accordance with Sharia principles. The second experiment was in the 1950s in the rural areas of Pakistan, and unfortunately, it did not continue. In 1962 the Malaysian government set up the Pilgrim's Management Fund to help prospective pilgrims save and profit from their money. The most successful and innovative experiment, however, was the establishment of MitGhamr Local Savings Bank in Egypt in 1963. It was marked as a milestone in the evolution of the modern Islamic banking system. Although the bank provided basic banking services such as deposit accounts, loan accounts direct investment, and social services, it was sufficient to meet the needs and requirements of the surrounding community. The bank provided clear evidence that there are Sharia-compliant financial solutions alternative to the conventional banking system and that these rules and principles are still applicable to meet the modern-day business and financial needs of the Muslim community. The interest-free banking system is one which operates according to the tenets/teachings of the Islamic faith. The most important feature of this banking system is that it is interest-free.

Apart from this feature, the interest-free banking system has other objectives – amongst which are the equitable distribution of income and wealth and increased equity participation in the economy (Clifford, 2008). It also prohibited investing in businesses that provide goods or services considered contrary to its principles, Haram such as businesses that sell alcohol or pork, or businesses that produce media such as gossip columns or pornography, which are contrary to Islamic values (Mohammed 2012).

According to the 2007 national census, the Muslim population comprises 33.9% of the total population (www.csa.gov.et accessed on 12/02/2016) in Ethiopia; this offers the opportunity for substantial customers that would patronize Islamic banking products. The national census shows in Ethiopia there is a huge potential for Islamic/interest free banking service. The study made by Mohammed (2012), has found out that there is need for Islamic banking products and services in Ethiopia. Beyond satisfying the need of Ethiopian customers Islamic banking will also create for Ethiopian government to gain diplomatic advantages to make financial dealings with Muslim dominated nations (Usmani, 2002). Islamic banking, on the one side, is being spread all over the world and regarded as a fastest growing market, on the other side; it is not free from issues, problems, and challenges. The Islamic banking faces serious problems to practice Islamic laws; proper interbank money market is not available and poor regulatory framework for interest free banking (Irfan, Majeed&Zaman 2014).

To satisfy the demand of Ethiopian Muslim customers, National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) in 2008 amended Ethiopian Banking Business Proclamation (592/2008) to include provision of IFB and it paved the way for the establishment of Islamic banking in Ethiopia. However, the declaration was amended by another declaration (SSB/51/2011) which prohibited the establishment of full-fledged Islamic financial institution but give the right to open the door for existing commercial

banks to create an interest-free banking wing. As (Senait,2015) explanation Zemzem bank which was expected to join the banking industry as a full-fledged interest free banking, was unable to start operation as the supervisory directive requires that interest-free banking be given alongside conventional banking service. However, Ethiopian Muslims are not part of this huge potential growth of that is occurring all corners of the world due to many factors in which lack of supportive regulatory and policy regimes that facilitate the establishment of Islamic financial institutions is the most important worth of mentioning.

Finally, responding to a strong public demand, the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) was expected to approve a directive that paves the way for the establishment of what was dubbed as the first Islamic bank in Ethiopia. A circulated draft form of the NBE directive has allowed Ethiopian nationals to establish a bank exclusively engaged in interest-free banking however, that hope was short living one as the finally issued draft currently does allow the establishment of full-fledged Islamic financial institution. However, the pastor the former directive has only opened the window for “existing commercial banks” to create an interest-free banking wing.

1.2. Statement of the problem

It is obvious that there are significant Muslim investors and borrowers in both Islamic and non-Islamic countries to warrant the attention of traditional banks who needs to serve such clients and capture a highly profitable allotment of a still relatively untapped market. This research mainly used to clear away some of the mysteries that surround Islamic financial services and shows how such financial system can fit side by side on a conventional interest-bearing banking system (Mohammed, 2012)

The fundamental aspect of Islamic banking is the absence of interest but there are other social, moral and ethical features claimed to be more "pure" or "enthusiastic" such as aiding a more fair and equitable distribution of income and wealth and avoiding undesirable sectors which provides product and service. There seems to be highly demand for Islamic banking products both in Muslim and non-Muslim majority countries. Why Islamic banking or interest free banking are not emerging in my country Ethiopia even if a significant number of demander for such banks. Now days, for a variety of reasons, including lack of focus from policy makers, lack of attention or the de-recognition of the government to the community which needs interest free banking , shortage of qualified and professional personal especially in the bank side and the one window operation of conventional banks to offer Islamic banking since the conventional banks are not prepared and encourage to spread Islamic banking therefore, they are just meeting the regulatory requirement to open Islamic window this need has gone largely unfilled for Ethiopian Muslims. The need for Islamic banking services and the prohibition of interest does not need any more justification as it just exists through the religious beliefs of Muslims.

But it is worth looking at the reasons put forward by some for Islamic banking to assist with understanding and innovation. For example, Islamic Banking will play a major role in the development of financial sector in a country like Ethiopia, where there is a significant Muslim population. Developing of Islamic financial institutions is advantageous to every economy because it enhances equitable distribute of income, operate interest free transactions and invest in only lawful investments and in real sector of the economy (Habib1992:1077-1087).

Though, Ethiopia is one of the fastest growing economies in Africa and also in the world, the range of the gap between rich and poor is still wide as in the case for other developing countries.

On the other hand, having only interest based conventional banking system and totally forgetting to cater or cast the financial services desire of the Muslim population is another obstacle to the development the financial sector in Ethiopia. Moreover, a sound, active and market-driven financial services industry can play an important role in creating opportunities and therefore addressing human development challenges of our societies by efficiently and equitably (Capital Ethiopia News - Islamic Banks to enter financial sector.mht)

Moreover, in addition to the evolving of the industry in this era of “globalization” where market, technological and regulatory environments are changing rapidly, there are other daunting challenges facing IFSIs which include lack of awareness and misconceptions, lack of qualified human resource for Shari’ compliance, lack of appropriate legal framework and tax neutrality, lack of enabling supervisory framework, unresolved fiqh issues as well as credibility and sustainability issues Islamic Financial Services Institutions (IFSIs)

There researches on the challenges, operational and risk aspects of Interest free banking in developed and emerging market countries are available. However, due to its novelty to Ethiopia the concept is not yet well researched and the literature is still few. Among these studies Mohammed in 2012 has studied the opportunities and Challenges of Islamic Banking in Ethiopia“ in his work discuss the potential challenges as: lack of awareness, regulatory, supervisory and institutional challenges, lack of support, lack of qualified human resource as well as wrongful association with specific religion and the global terrorism but, this study was conducted before the practical introduction of the full-fledged IFB in Ethiopia. Therefore, it was not based on actual observation of facts. And also Akmel Hailu’s (2015) study is about “challenges and prospects of Islamic banking for resource mobilization in Ethiopian commercial banks.

“The study focuses on challenges and opportunities of IFB only on resource mobilization other challenges and opportunities are not well addressed. On the other hand a research by Debebe Alemu (2015) who studied the factors affecting customers’ use of IFB in Ethiopia and found out that 100% of IFB account holders were all Muslims. Evidently, the failure of banks to meritoriously serve the Ethiopian Muslim population hinders the development of the Muslim inhabited areas in particular and the economy of the nation as a whole. The study conducted by Akmel is about impact assessment on the attitude towards IFB usage which does not address the current problem at hand. Therefore, the above researchers address their case studies before the permission of Islamic or IFB as a full- fledged base. Because of this fact the researchers they don’t have full information about the IFB system.

This study therefore, attempts to fill the above research gap by investigating the prospects, challenges and opportunities of Islamic banking (interest free banking) from the service provider’s and from the customer (the service recipients) viewpoints. Therefore, as the idea of interest free banking is still new for the economy, new for the society, and new even for business practitioners it is necessary look at the opinions regarding prospect, opportunities and challenges about the services and products offered under Islamic (Interest free) banking by Ethiopian commercial banks and their regularity with the original Interest free banking law. It is equally important to ascertain the challenges and opportunities surrounding the practice of IFB so as to formulate alternative solutions for its effectiveness. The study tried to analyze the above mentioned points as well as the directives and the proclamation that is used for performing the Islamic or interest free banking by considering the case of commercial banks operating in West

Addis Ababa District which are one of the first full-fledged banks to start interest free banking system in Ethiopia and who starts working as a full-fledged.

1.3. Research Objectives

1.3.1. The general Objective

The general objective of this study is to assess the prospects and challenges facing Islamic banking in Ethiopia. The study tries to assess the potentiality, prospects, opportunities and challenges that IFSIs face in the Ethiopian financial services industry. Therefore, this study tries to find what are the prospects, challenges and problems that Islamic banking model faces in Ethiopia.

1.3.2. The specific Objectives

The research study addresses the following specific objectives;

- ✚ To examine the prospect of Interest Free Banking system in the West Addis Ababa District
- ✚ To analyze and identify the major obstacle and challenge that faces the establishments well as the operations of Islamic banking services in West Addis Ababa District.
- ✚ To assess the availability of demand for IFB products other than those currently provided by the bank.

1.4. Research Questions

In order to achieve the intended objectives of the study and to address the research problem properly, certain research questions are designed accordingly. In light of this, the research ponders to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the demand level for IFB products other than those currently provided?
2. What are the major obstacle and challenge that faces the establishment as well as the operations of Islamic banking services in Ethiopia?
3. What are the challenges which the bank and customers faces in delivering and using interest free banking?
4. Does lack of awareness and proper understanding about the operations of Islamic banking pose serious challenge to the success of Islamic banking in West Addis Ababa District?

1.5. Significance of the study

The findings of the study will be useful in many ways and too many parties. First of all this findings used for the government how to formulate and make a policies regarding the IFB It will also benefit those concerned policy makers to formulate necessary and solution-oriented policies that will in fact have a benefit to all citizens. To be specific in this regard, this study will help in making decisions with regard to fast tracking policy dimensions that help not only realizing the establishment of Islamic banking but also the effective operation as well as supervision of Islamic financial services institutions.

Secondly the results of the study will help the Muslim population in general and the business community in particular, the findings used by creating awareness about Islamic banks or IFB system.

Thirdly this study tries to give an investment tip to both current as well as potential investors to target this untapped market which will help in improving the economy, living standard of citizens as well as competition and efficiency.

Finally the other important benefit that the findings of this study will have is its contribution to knowledge building and academic research by helping other researchers to undertake further detailed investigation and a spring board on the subject and providing relevant empirical evidences.

1.6. Scope of the study

Based on the objectives the present study collected and analyzed the information about Islamic (interest free) banking, what kind of role and progress it has been playing in Ethiopia, in what way its financial products and services are available to the community and finally what kind of prospect's, challenges and opportunities it has been facing in the current scenario. The study mainly focuses on the geographical area of West Addis Ababa District City Administration of Addis Ababa, specifically in the Kolfekeraniyo Sub-city selected commercial banks.

1.7. Description of the study area

To pioneer and examine the prospects, opportunities and challenges of Islamic banking model in Ethiopia, this research targets Addis Ababa City administration specifically West Addis Ababa District of CBE IFB as survey participants. In order to achieve the intended objectives of the study and to address the research problem properly, the researcher uses some newly emerging IFB Commercial banks.

1.8. Limitation and Delimitation

1.8.1. Limitation of the study

The potential limitation in performing this study includes but not limited to; lack of relevant and exhausted related research works on the title especially in our country Ethiopia. The other limitation is most of the participants don't have clear understanding about the purpose and the intention of the study and there is inherent risk of extreme reservations in full participation, if any, due to the high sensitivity and versatility when it comes to religious matters, especially in this time.

1.8.2. Delimitation of the study

The scope of this study is delimited to only assessing the prospects, opportunity and challenges of Islamic banking in Ethiopia by taking Addis Ababa based CBE specifically West Addis Ababa district some newly emerged interest free banking as survey participants to this research. The study will only include data collected from the participants of the study through questionnaires that will be distributed and administered to them in addition to the accepted financial and economic theories from secondary sources. However, it does not attempt to provide any moral justification, rationale or even establish clear rules as to what is Islamic and therefore Hallal and what is un-Islamic and therefore prohibited or Haram.

1.9. Organization of the paper

This research paper is organized in to five chapters, the first chapter deals about the introduction of the study that is background, statement of the problem, research objective, and research questions significance, scope of the study area and Limitation and delimitation.

The second chapter discusses the conceptual, theoretical and empirical literatures about Islamic Banking. The third chapter is about the methodology of the research that is the research design, sampling technique, method of data collection, data collection instruments, method of data analysis and so on.

The fourth chapter of the paper presents the findings and result as well as the quantitative and qualitative data analysis. Finally the fifth chapter deals with the summary, conclusion and recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO

2. RELATED RETERATURE REVIEW

2.1. THEORETICAL REVIEW

In literature review the researcher will try to focus the concept, scope, ideology, principles of Islamic banking, difference between Islamic and Conventional banking and how Islamic banking emerged in Ethiopia. Challenges face by Islamic banking during embryonic stage and its future expectations will also be discussed. As the same time in this chapter, also will be reviewed and discusses the literature concerning the prospects and challenges of Islamic Banking in Ethiopia and elsewhere will be presented. The relevant literature will be collected from different secondary sources and it includes material about the Islamic economic model, evolution of Islamic banking, key financial instruments, and Islamic banking literature versus practice, empirical evidences on Islamic banking, challenges as well as the need for Islamic banking in Ethiopia will be analyzed in the following sections of this chapter.

2.1.1. History of Islamic banking and finance system (Theoretical)

The chapter is related with literature of Islamic banking and finance system. This part of research will present the Islamic banking and finance principles and methods to fund the banks and finance institutions. As mentioned early, Islamic bank follows Sharia principle, which is based on profit and loss sharing principle. Islamic Finance started in the 1970s in the Middle East and North Africa region to primarily provide banking services to the Muslim population. In fact, the basic idea of Islamic banking can be stated simply. The operations of Islamic financial institutions primarily are based on a PLS principle. An Islamic bank does not charge interest but rather participates in the yield resulting from the use of funds. The depositors also share in the profits of the bank according to a predetermined ratio. There is thus a partnership between the Islamic bank and its depositors, on one side, and between the bank and its investment clients, on the other side, as a manager of depositors' resources in productive uses. (Kettell B.2011).

The mid-twentieth century writing on Islamic finance has given rise to practical discussions on the subject, which has in turn raised the issue of replacing conventional financial practices with alternatives that are in compliance with Islamic law. Sharia' denotes the Islamic law that governs

all aspects of Muslims' lives. It is derived from the Quran and the Sunnah, which is the saying and examples set by the Prophet Mohammed.

The development of modern Western banking goes back to the mid seventeenth century, when development in mathematics and statistics provided powerful tools for financial mathematical science. These tools were developed over 300 years, and as a consequence, we have a robust interest-based financial system in place. At the same time, the legal and regulatory framework for the Western banking model has come a long way (Altiby O. 2010)

Evolution of Islamic Banking started initially from Egypt. It was due to the efforts of Ahmad El Najjar who started saving bank based on profit sharing in one of the town in Egypt named MitGhamr in 1963. Within 4 years i.e. until 1967 nine more banks were developed in Egypt. All these banks were functioning on same pattern i.e. none of them were charging or paying interest. These banks were making partnership with others institutions / persons/ entities to invest in trade and industry. The return so derived is shared with investors / depositors. Apparently these were not exclusively Islamic Bank or Conventional Bank but categorized as Saving Investment Institutions. In 1971 The Nasir Social Bank was established in Egypt was named as 'Interest Free Commercial Bank' without disclosing any reference to Islamic Banking, Non Interest Banking, or Sharia principles in its charter. Later in 1974 Islamic Development Bank (IDB) was established by the efforts of Organization of Islamic Countries (OIC). It was not established with the aim to promote Islamic Banking only but it came into being largely to finance for projects in member countries.

However, the principle for its formation was interest free operations based on Sharia principles.

2.1.2. Six key Islamic Banking principles

The principles of Islamic finance are established in the Quran, which Muslims believe are the exact Words of God as revealed to the Prophet Mohammed (**PBUOH**). These are Islamic principles of finance can be narrowed down to six individual concepts.

- ✚ Predetermined loan repayments as interest (Riba) is prohibited.
- ✚ Profit and loss sharing is at the heart of the Islamic system.
- ✚ Making money out of money is unacceptable
- ✚ Speculative behavior is prohibited.
- ✚ Only Sharia's-approved contracts are acceptable.
- ✚ Contracts are sacred. (Kettell B, 33)

2.1.3. Predetermined Payments are prohibited

Any predetermined payment over and above the actual amount of principal is prohibited. Islam allows only one kind of loan and that is qard al Hassan (literally meaning good loan), where by the lender does not charge any interest or additional amount over the money lent. Traditional Muslim Jurists have construed this principle so strictly that, according to one Islamic scholar. The principle, derived from this quotation, emphasizes that any associated or indirect benefits that could potentially accrue to the lender, from lending money, are also prohibited. (Kettell B, 2011)

2.1.4. Profit and Loss sharing

The principle here is that the lender must share in the profits or losses arising out of the enterprise for which the money was lent. Islam encourages Muslims to invest their money and to become partners in order to share profits and risks in a business instead of becoming creditors. Islamic finance is based on the belief that the provider of capital and the user of capital should equally share the risk of business ventures, whether those are industries, service companies or simple trade deals. This is unlike the interest-based commercial banking system, where all the pressure is on the borrower who must pay back the loan, with the agreed interest, regardless of the success or failure of his venture. The objective of all this is to encourage investments and thereby provide a stimulus to the economy and encourage entrepreneurs to maximize their efforts to make them succeed. (Kettell B, 2011).

2.1.5. Making money out of money is Not Acceptable

Making money from money is not Islamically acceptable. Money, in Islam, is only a medium of exchange, a way of defining the value of a thing. It has no value in itself, and therefore should not be allowed to generate more money, via fixed interest payments, simply by being deposited in a bank or lent to someone else. (Kettell B, 2011).

2.1.6. Uncertainty is prohibited

Gharar (uncertainty, risk or speculation) is also prohibited, and so any transaction entered into should be free from these elements. Contracting parties should have perfect knowledge of the counter-values intended to be exchanged as a result of their transactions. In this context the term counter-values is used in the sense of something being deferred, either the price paid or the commodity delivered. Deferral of payment is an acceptable form of debt under Islam, in contrast to predetermined debt in conventional finance. (Kettell B, 2011).

2.1.7. Only Sharia 'a-Approved Contracts are Acceptable

Conventional banking is secular in its orientation. In contrast, in the Islamic system, all economic agents should work within the ethical system of Islam. Islamic banks are no exception. As such, they cannot finance any project that conflicts with the Islamic moral value system. For example, Islamic banks are not allowed to finance a wine factory, a casino, a night club or any other activity prohibited by Islam or known to be harmful to society. (Kettell B, 2011).

2.1.8. Sanctity of Contract

Many verses in the Holy Qur'an encourage trade and commerce, and the attitude of Islam is that there should be no impediment to honest and legitimate trade and business. Just as Islam regulates and influences all other spheres of life, so it also governs the conduct of business and commerce. Muslims have a moral obligation to conduct their business activities in accordance with the requirements of their religion. They should be fair, honest and just towards others. A special obligation exists upon vendors because there is no doctrine of caveat emptor in Islam. (Brian Ketell, 2011).

2.1.9. Structure of Islamic Financial system

The Islamic financial system has evolved into a viable and vibrant component of the overall financial system, complementing the conventional financial system. The rapid progress of the Islamic banking system, accentuated by significant expansion and developments in Islamic banking and finance has become increasingly more important in meeting the changing

requirements of the new economy. Four structures have been used to assist Muslims to acquire their homes in a manner consistent with the Sharia (Omar M, 2013).

- ✚ Mudharabah
- ✚ Murabaha
- ✚ IjarawaIqtina
- ✚ Diminishing Musharakh

2.1.10. Mudharaba

The basic concept on which earlier Islamic Banking functions depended and flourished was Mudharaba. Mudharaba, according to jurists, is a social contract whereby one gives his property to another to carry on business therewith and the profit to be shared between them according to the specked terms such as one-half, one-third or so. In Mudharaba, the entire loss is always attributed to and deductible from the capital Mudharib and thus agent has nothing to lose except his labor.

There is yet another marked difference between Mudharaba and other kinds of partnership; whereas all other kinds of partnership may consist of two or more persons, Mudharaba consists of only two – one is the financier and the other his agent. The financier invests his capital and the agent his skill. Whereas in other partnerships each partner is an agent for each other, there is no case of Mudharaba. The capital must be surrendered to the mudharib so that he may handle it alone (without any interference, whatsoever, from the lender or principal). Loss, if any should be assigned to the capital, the agent or Mudharib will not bear it, neither should Mudharib invest anything of his own nor bear any material loss. The concept of Mudharaba is a simple system of partnership, which will work by the distribution of half yearly profits to the account holders/customers who in fact are the shareholders to the Bank. The bank will accept deposits from the community both for safekeeping and profit sharing purposes ,Audu Bello et al (2014)

A certain personal loans while the major portion will be utilized to meet the credit requirements of the business and the industry. The interest-free banks will provide credit facilities and perform all the functions of commercial banks. Being partner in business and industry, they will supervise the progress of work and under the vigilance of Bank staff the chances of loss are minimized. The profit sharing principle will provide incentive to the investors who will invest their money in the Bank Audu Bello et al. (2014)

The partners in such banks shall have mutual gain and mutual loss whereas in the modern banking the losses are borne by the borrowers alone and the lender always stands to gain. Mudharabah relationship is more just than the creditor debtor relationship because:

- I.** Both parties agree on the ratio in which profits will be shared between them.
- II.** The treatment of both parties is uniform in the event of loss, since if the provider of the capital suffers a reduction of his principal, the manager is deprived of a reward for his labor, time and effort.
- III.** Both parties are treated equally if there is any violation of the agreement. If the manager violates anyone of the stipulated conditions, or if he does not work, or is instrumental in causing loss to the business by negligence or bad management, he will have to bear the responsibility for the safe return of the whole amount in question. If, on the other hand, the provider of the capital violates any of the stipulated conditions, for example, by withdrawing his funds before the stipulated time, or by not providing part or full funds at

the promised time, etc., he will have to pay the manager a reward equivalent to what he would have earned in similar work. Mudharabah is the basis of modern Islamic banking on a two-tier basis.

- IV. Profits are distrusted between the bank and entrepreneur on predetermined ratio. All Losses are born by the supplier of the fund (bank) as long as there has been negligence on the part of the entrepreneur (Bala et.al (2009: 34).

1st tier: The depositors put their money into the bank's investment account and agree to share profits with it. In this case, the depositors are the providers of the capital and the bank functions as the manager of funds.

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-1: Schematic representation of Midaraba agreement for 1st tier

2nd tier :Entrepreneurs seek finance from the bank for their businesses on the condition that profits accruing from their business will be shared between them and the bank in a mutually settled proportion, but that any loss will be borne by the bank only. In this case, the bank functions as the provider of capital and the entrepreneur functions as the manager. Mudharabah however is also a risky proposition as the partner may lead the bank to other encumbrances. As explained by Pollock, such person may bind his firm by any of the following acts:

He may sell any goods or personal chattels of the firm.

- I. He may purchase on account of the firm any goods of any kind necessary for or usually employed in the business carried on by it.
- II. He may borrow money on credit of the firm. He may, for the purpose, pledge any goods or personal chattels belonging to the firm. Audu Bello et al. (2014)

Due to the risk inherent in the Mudharaba transactions and the inability of this mode of financing

to cater to the requirements of modern complex Organizational structures other Islamic Interest-free mechanisms like Mudharabah and PLS are also suggested. These are briefly discussed as under:

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-2: Schematic representation of Mudharabah agreement for 2nd tier

2.1.11. Murabaha

Literally, Murabaha means a profitable sale and it is also sometimes called Bai'a Bithaman Ajil, meaning deferred payment sale. Murabaha, in this context, is essentially an installment sales contract for property. Of all Islamic approaches to the question of leveraged home acquisition, this method is most consistent with the conventional house purchase processes. Murabaha is a form of asset finance that involves the lender purchasing the asset, back to back with a sale of the asset, to the borrower, at an increased price. This increased price reflects the interest otherwise payable. (Omar M, 2013).

Murabahain ancient Islamic connotations referred to a particular kind of simple sale and had no relevance whatsoever with a transaction of financing. In view of the difficulties and risks visualized in adopting Mudharaba and PLS system of Islamic banking on a large scale, in recent times, the Murabaha, for all practical purposes was transformed from the sale transaction to a mode of financing.

2.1.12. Financing on Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) basis - Musharakah

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-3: Schematic representation of Murabaha agreement

2.1.13. Financing on profit and loss sharing (PLS) basis Musharakh

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-4:-Schematic representation of profit and loss sharing

The real alternate to interest on loans in an Islamic framework is financing on Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) basis- a shift from debt based transaction to investment based funding. It is believed that the financing on PLS system or Equity- Participation system of Islamic banking in a conducive environment would not only ensure a healthier financing portfolio and of course higher rates of return to depositors but would also lead to optimum allocation of resources for over-all economic growth and welfare of the society, individually and collectively. The bulk of financing by Islamic banks has to be equity oriented. In this mode of financing, the losses are shared by the financier along with the entrepreneur in the ratio of their respective capitals. The profits are, however, shared in an agreed ratio. The rates of returns are thus replaced by ratios. PLS or Equity-participation systems had been proposed at various times of economic crises in the United States and Latin America. The most ardent proponent of these was American Economist, Henry Simons (1899 – 1946), who, in the 1930s, argued that the traditional fractional reserve banking system was inherently unstable and should be replaced by two separate financial institutions: Hussain et al. (2015).

2.1.14. Leasing (ijarah or ijar)

Figure **Error! No text of specified style in document.-5** :-Schematic representation of Lease (Ijarah)

Legally, the lease contract is not a sale of the object, but rather a sale of the usufruct (the right to use the object) for a specified period of time.

The use of usufruct is permissible in Islam, as evidenced by the various verses and Hadith. The following Hadith narrated by Ahmad, AbuDawud, establishes it and Al Nasa'I on the authority of Sa'd: The farmers during the time of the Prophet (**pbuh**) used to pay rent for the land in water and seeds. He (**pbuh**) forbade them from doing that, and ordered them to use gold and silver (money) to pay the rent. Care must be taken by the financial institutions to ensure that the contract abides by all the restrictions set in the Sharia like; sub-leasing requires the permission of the lessor, late payment penalties must be handled very carefully to avoid Riba, etc. Recently, Muslim jurists have provided an Islamic alternative to conventional leasing-purchase agreements. In this contract, a lease is written as discussed above; with an additional promise by the lessor that he will agree to sell the leased object at the end of the lease at a pre-determined residual value. The promise is binding on the lessor only, and the lessee has the option of purchasing the item at the end of the lease, or returning it to the lessor. (M TaqqiUsmani – 1998).

2.1.15. Other Key Islamic Financial Instruments

It is deemed acceptable to charge higher prices for deferred payments. Such transactions are regarded as trades and not loans. Property financing on such a deferred payment basis is called Baimuajjal'Hussain et al. (2015).

2.1.16. 'Bai'bithamanajil' (deferred payment sale)

This concept refers to the sale of goods on a deferred payment basis at a price, which includes a profit margin agreed to by both parties. Like 'Bai'-al-'inah', this concept is also used under an Islamic financing facility. Interest payment can be avoided as the customer is paying the sale price which is not the same as interest charged on a loan. Mohammed (2012).

2.1.17. 'Bai' al 'inah' (sale and buy-back agreement)

"Bai' al inah" is a financing facility with an underlying buy and sell transactions between the financier and the customer. The financier buys an asset from the customer on spot basis. The price paid by the financier constitutes the disbursement under the facility. Subsequently the asset is sold to the customer on a deferred-payment basis and the price is payable in installments. The second sale serves to create the obligation on the part of the customer under the facility. Mohammed, (2012)

2.1.18. 'Ijarahthumma al bai' (hire purchase)

Parties enter into contracts that come into effect serially, to form a complete lease/buyback transaction. The first contract is an 'Ijarah' that outlines the terms for leasing or renting over a fixed period, and the second contract is a 'Bai' that triggers a sale or purchase once the term of the 'Ijarah' is complete⁵³. The bank generates a profit by determining in advance the cost of the item, its residual value at the end of the term and the time value or profit margin for the money being invested in purchasing the product to be leased for the intended term. The combining of these three figures becomes the basis for the contract between the Bank and the client for the initial lease contract.(Hassan andSkully2007).

2.1.19. 'Ijarah-wal-iqtina'

A contract under which an "Islamic bank" provides equipment, building, or other assets to the client against an agreed rental together with a unilateral undertaking by the bank or the client that at the end of the lease period, the ownership in the asset would be transferred to the lessee. The undertaking or the promise does not become an integral part of the lease contract to make it conditional. The rentals as well as the purchase price are fixed in such manner that the bank gets back its principal sum along with profit over the period of lease. Ahmed (2000)

2.1.20. 'Bai-salam'

When a manufacturer seeks to finance the production of goods he seeks „Baisalamfinancing. This involves the bank paying for the producer's goods at a discount before they have been delivered or even made .Bai-salam' means a contract in which advance payment is made for goods to be delivered later on. The seller undertakes to supply some specific goods to the buyer at a future date in exchange of an advance price fully paid at the time of contract. It is necessary that the quality of the commodity intended to be purchased is fully specified leaving no ambiguity leading to dispute. The objects of this sale are goods and cannot be gold, silver, or currencies based on these metals. Barring this, 'Bai-Salam' covers almost everything that is capable of being definitely described as to quantity, quality, and workmanship. As Hussain et al (2015)

2.1.21. 'Musawamah'

'Musawamah' is the negotiation of a selling price between two parties without reference by the seller to either costs or asking price. While the seller may or may not have full knowledge of the cost of the item being negotiated, they are under no obligation to reveal these costs as part of the negotiation process.

This difference in obligation by the seller is the key distinction between „Murabaha' and Musawamah' with all other rules as described in “Murayama”remaining the same Musawamah' is the most common type of trading negotiation seen in Islamic commerce Mohammed (2012).

2.1.22. 'Certificates of sale'

It has been suggested that consumers buying consumables on credit would issue certificates of sale' similar to letters of credit. These could be encashed by the seller at the bank at a discount. This seems very similar in structure to „Bai-salam'Hussain et al. (2015).

2.1.23. No fee accounts

There is a substantial Muslim population in South Africa and they are serviced by two small Islamic banks. The main product being offered is the "no fee" current account which is also provided by the conventional banks by arrangement. Transaction charges are waived and interest is not paid on current accounts. Interest is charged on loans by conventional banks. These are similar to Special demand deposit provided by the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia. Mohammed Muhammad 2012.

2.1.24. Hibah'gifts'

Gifts to depositors are given entirely at the discretion of the Islamic banks on the basis of the minimum balance. These gifts may be monetary or non-monetary and are based on the banks' returns⁵⁶.This is a token given voluntarily by a debtor to a creditor in return for a loan. “Hibah

'usually arises in practice when Islamic banks voluntarily pay their customers a 'gift' on savings account balances, representing a portion of the profit made by using those savings account balances in other activities. It is important to note that while it appears similar to interest, and may, in effect, have the same outcome, "Hibah" is a voluntary payment made (or not made) at the bank's discretion, and cannot be 'guaranteed'. However, the opportunity of receiving high Hibah' will draw in customers' savings, providing the bank with capital necessary to create its profits; if the ventures are profitable, then some of those profits may be gifted back to its customers "Hibah" <http://www.rhbislamicbank.com>.

2.1.25. Qardhassan (good/benevolent loan)

This is a loan extended on a goodwill basis, and the debtor is only required to repay the amount borrowed. However, the debtor may, at his or her discretion, pay an extra amount beyond the principal amount of the loan (without promising it) as a token of appreciation to the creditor. In the case that the debtor does not pay an extra amount to the creditor, this transaction is true interest-free loan.

Some Muslims consider this to be the only type of loan that does not violate the prohibition on "riba" since it is the one type of loan that truly does not compensate the creditor for the time value of money. Qardhassan literally mean good loan (Bala et al (2009: 34).

2.1.26. 'Sukuk'(Islamic bonds)

'Sukuk', plural of "Sack" is the Arabic name for financial certificates that are the Islamic equivalent of bonds. However, fixed-income, interest-bearing bonds are not permissible in Islam. Hence, "Sukuk" are securities that comply with the Islamic law "Sharia" and its investment principles, which prohibit the charging or paying of interest The United Kingdom became the first non-Muslim country to issue a sovereign sukuk in 2014.

2.1.27. Takaful (Islamic Insurance)

"Takaful" is an alternative form of cover that a Muslim can avail himself against the risk of loss due to misfortunes. Takaful is based on the idea that what is uncertain with respect to an individual may cease to be uncertain with respect to a very large number of similar individuals. Insurance by combining the risks of many people enables each individual to enjoy the advantage provided by the law of large numbers see Takaful for details (Natalie Schoon2016).

2.1.28. Islamic equity funds

Islamic investment equity funds market is one of the fastest-growing sectors within the Islamic financial system. Currently, there are more than 100 Islamic equity funds worldwide. The total assets managed through these funds currently exceed US\$5 billion and is growing by 12–15% per annum. With the continuous interest in the Islamic financial system, there are positive signs that more funds will be launched. Some Western majors have just joined the fray or are thinking of launching similar Islamic equity products .Despite these successes, this market has seen a record of poor marketing as emphasis is on products and not on addressing the needs of investors. Over the last few years, quite a number of funds have closed down.

Most of the funds tend to target high net worth individuals and corporate institutions, with minimum investments ranging from US\$50,000 to as high as US\$1 million. Target markets for Islamic funds vary; some cater for their local markets, e.g., Malaysia and Gulf-based investment funds.

Others clearly target the Middle East and Gulf regions, neglecting local markets and have been accused of failing to serve Muslim communities (Iraj T and M. Kabir, 2011) and (Bala et al, 2009: 23).

2.2. Retail Islamic Banking Products

2.2.1. Current Account (Alwadhiah)

At a retail level, Islamic banks provide current, savings, and investment accounts. The current account is basically safekeeping or "Al-wadhiah" account and used for day to day cash management. In 'Al-Wadhiah', a bank is deemed as a keeper and trustee of the funds. A person deposits funds in the bank and the bank guarantees refund of the entire amount of the deposit, or any part of the outstanding amount, when the depositor demands it and permits the bank to use the depositors' money. It is very similar to such accounts in conventional banks. No return is paid to depositors, however, at the bank's discretion, may be rewarded with Hibah' (Omar M, 2013).

2.2.2. Account Savings

Alwadhiah' structures are also used for higher return savings account. Banks may as they see fit pay the savers a return, depending on their own profitability. This seems to be allowed as the bank's payment, if any, is level and is not determined in advance. (Omar M, 2013). And (Abdul-Gafoor, 1995:14).

2.2.3. Investment Account

The investment accounts use the "Mudharaba" format. Deposits are fixed term and cannot be cashed in before maturity. In practice there are only profit sharing and no loss sharing for retail investors. The lower risk means a lower profit share. There are considerable variations on the "Mudharaba" principle and the frequency of payment and declaration of profits (BKettel, 2011).

2.2.4. Islamic Laws on Trading

The "Qur'an" prohibits gambling (games of chance involving money) and insuring ones 'health or property (also considered a game of chance).

The "hadith", in addition to prohibiting gambling (games of chance), also prohibits 'bayu al-gharar' (trading in risk, where the Arabic word "gharar" is taken to mean "risk" or excessive uncertainty). The 'Hanafimadhab' (legal school) in Islam defines "gharar" as that whose consequences are hidden."

The Shafil egal school defined "gharar" as that whose nature and consequences are hidden" or "that which admits two possibilities, with the less desirable one being more likely.

"The Hanbali school defined it as "that whose consequences are unknown" or "that which is undeliverable, whether it exists or not." IbnHazm of the Zahiri School wrote "Gharar" is where the buyer does not know what he bought, or the seller does not know what he sold." The modern scholar of Islam, Professor Mustafa Al-Zarqa, wrote that "Gharar' is the sale of probable items whose existence or characteristics are not certain, due to the risky nature that makes the trade similar to gambling. Other modern scholars, such as Dr. Sami al-Suwailem, have used Game

Theory to try and reach a more measured definition of “Gharar, defining it as "a zero-sum game with unequal payoffs"(Iqbal&Mirkahor, 2011).

2.2.5. Microfinance

Microfinance is a key concern for Muslims states and recently Islamic banks also. Microfinance is ideologically compatible with Islamic finance, capable of “Sharia compliancy’, and possesses a sizeable potential market. Islamic microfinance tools can enhance security of tenure and contribute to transformation of lives of the poor. The use of interest found in conventional microfinance products and services can easily be avoided by creating microfinance hybrids delivered on the basis of the Islamic contracts of “Mudharaba’, „Musharakh’, and “Murabaha’. Already, several microfinance institutions (MFIs) such as FINCA Afghanistan have introduced Islamic-compliant financial instruments that accommodate “Sharia’ criteria. Ali and A.C Seman.(2008)

2.2.6. Risk Management and Innovations in Islamic Financial Services

Islamic financial institutions have taken numerous efforts to be innovative vehicle for their respective economies. These institutions introduced several products since the year2006, considered to be the first in the world in order to sustain their customer's loyalty and perceptions. New investment models and business tools are being developed by Islamic financial experts which are not only hundred percent Sharia compliant but also highly profitable. These tools or investment portfolios can be used both by Muslim and non-Muslim alike.AggarwalRajesh &YousefTarik, (2000).

2.2.7. Islamic Derivatives

For example, with the help of Bahrain-based International Islamic Financial Market and New York-based International Swaps and Derivatives Association, global standards for Islamic derivative were set in 2010 Ahmed, Z 1987a, ‘Interest-free banking

2.2.7.1. Wiqa’ Forward Rate Agreement (WFRA)

Considered to be first of its kind, was introduced as a ‘Sharia-compliant’ financial hedging tool on August 15, 2006tofacilitate their in-house risk management and in the same time ensures that customers have access to hedge profit rates whilst enhancing their (customer) balance sheet management. By having WFRA, Islamic Banks minimize their risk exposure to fixed rate payments, by swapping some of them with a conventional bank (non-“Sharia-compliant“) for floating rate payments. Akhtar, A R 1988, The Law and Practice of Interest-free Banking

2.2.7.2. Wiqa’ Profit Rate Swaps (WPRS)

As an extension from WFRA, Wiqa’ Profit Rate Swap (WPRS) was also introduced. It is an agreement between two parties to exchange a series of profit payments denominated in a single currency for another series of profit payments denominated in the same currency, based on a notional principal amount over agreed tenor. Al-Omar, F & Abdel-Haq, M 1996, Islamic Banking

2.2.7.3. Islamic Cross Currencies Swap (ICCS)

Enhancing the capabilities for Islamic Hedging, those Islamic financial institutions pioneering Islamic financial services and Risk management successfully initiated the first ICCS in the

world, where the bank and its customers altering their exposure to interest rate fluctuations, by swapping fixed-rate obligations for floating rate obligations.

This product heavily being used with the expectation of a change in interstate's or the relationships between them, where on the Islamic framework the existence of interest rates being eliminated with Profit Rate." Commodity Murabaha" will be used as the main vehicle for ICCS and WFRA .Bashir, M 1999.

2.2.7.4. Commodity 'Murabaha'

Commodity "Murabaha" is a trade-related transaction. The main structure of this transaction will be based on the actual trading of steel in London Stock Exchange through a nominated broker. The trade entails a spot purchase of "Sharia" compliant commodities for immediate delivery and forward sale on deferred payment term (cost plus basis).El-Ashker, A 1995

2.2.8. SMART chip Card

Pioneering Islamic financial institutions have introduced Credit Card Chip Based (SMART Chip). The SMART Chip Card is based on three "Sharia' concepts, and is considered to be the first in the world:

- BaiInah- The sale of the land by the bank on a deferred payment basis, which the bank then buys back the land by cash at a lower price
- Wadiah- Guaranteed safe custody of cash by cardholder, which allows the cardholder to make use of the cash.
- Qardhul Hassan - It is the over limit usage of cash by the cardholder. The cardholder will not be levied with extra charges or fees but will be required to repay the over limit amount used. Khan, M M&Bhatti, M I, 2008

2.2.8.1. Services of the Card

The services offered by the Bank Islam Card include; Retail purchases, Cash withdrawal facilities ATMs, Easy payment accessibility and cash withdrawals at any branches and ATMs of the Bank, Transfer of balance service; Emergency cash withdrawal and emergency card replacement when overseas; and 24 hours customer service.

2.2.9. Sharia Advisory Council/Consultant

Islamic banks and banking institutions that offer Islamic banking products and services (IBS banks) are required to establish a "Sharia" Supervisory Board (SSB) to advise them and to ensure that the operations and activities of the banking institutions comply with "Sharia" principles. A number of "Sharia" advisory firms have now emerged to offer "Sharia' advisory services to the institutions offering Islamic financial services. Issue of independence, impartiality and conflicts of interest have also been recently voiced. The "WDIBF" World Database for Islamic Banking and Finance has been developed to provide information about all the websites related to this type of banking. Judgment on Riba Case Review 2002, Sharia Law Reports, Lahore.

2.2.10. Islamic Banking Literature versus Practice

Recent years have brought an increasing flow of empirical studies of Islamic banking. The earliest systematic empirical work was undertaken by Khan (1983). Khan's study showed that Islamic banks had little difficulty in devising practices in conformity with Sharia.

Khan's study reported profit rates ranging from 9 to 20 per cent which were competitive with conventional banks in the corresponding areas.

The rates of return to depositors varied between 8 and 15 per cent, which were quite comparable with the rates of return offered by conventional banks. Khan's study revealed that Islamic banks had a preference for trade finance and real estate investments. The study also revealed a strong preference for quick returns, which is understandable in view of the fact that these newly established institutions were anxious to report positive results even in the early years of operation.

2.2.11. Empirical Evidences on Islamic Banking

Nienhaus (1988) suggests that the relative profitability of Islamic banks, especially in the Middle East in recent years, was to a large extent due to the property (real estate) boom. He has cited cases of heavy losses which came with the crash of the property sector. The IMF study earlier by Iqbal and Mirakhor (1987) also contains extremely interesting empirical observations, although these are confined to the experience of Iran and Pakistan, both of which have attempted to Islamize the entire banking system on a comprehensive basis. Iran switched to Islamic banking in August 1983 with a three-year transition period. Iqbal and Mirakhor have noted that the conversion to Islamic modes has been much slower on the asset than on the deposit side. The Pakistani experience differs from the Iranian one in that Pakistan had opted for a gradual Islamization process.

The Pakistani model took care to ensure that the new modes of financing did not upset the basic functioning and structure of the banking system. This and the gradual pace of transition, according to the authors, made it easier for the Pakistani banks to adapt to the new system. The rate of return on profit-and-loss sharing (PLS) deposits appears not only to have been in general higher than the interest rate before Islamization but also to have varied between banks, the differential indicating the degree of competition in the banking industry.

The authors noted that the PLS system and the new modes of financing had accorded considerable flexibility to banks and their clients. Once again the study concluded that the effectiveness of monetary policy in Pakistan was not impaired by the changeover. The IMF study, however, expressed considerable uneasiness about the concentration of bank assets on short-term trade credits rather than on long-term financing. The authors found this undesirable, not only because it is inconsistent with the intentions of the new system, but also because the heavy concentration on a few assets might increase risks and destabilize the asset portfolios.

There are also some small case studies of Islamic banks operating in Bangladesh (Huq 1986), Egypt (Mohammad 1986), Malaysia (Halim 1988b), Pakistan (Khan 1986), and Sudan (Salama 1988b). These studies reveal interesting similarities and differences.

For example, the current accounts and Savings deposits in all cases are operated on the principles of alwadhiah. There are also interesting variations in the pattern of resource utilization, profit-

sharing ratios and the modes of payment from place to place and from time to time. A striking common feature of all these banks is that their investment deposits are mostly short-term, reflecting the depositors' preference for assets in as liquid a form as possible. The case studies also show that the structure of the clientele has been skewed in favor of the more affluent segment of society, no doubt because the banks are located mainly in metropolitan centers with small branch networks.

The two main problems identified by the case studies are the absence of suitable noninterest-based financial instruments for money and capital market transactions and the high rate of borrower delinquency. The delinquency problem appears to be real and serious. Murabaha payments have often been held up because late payments cannot be penalized, in contrast to the interest system in which delayed payments would automatically mean increased interest payments. In the Southeast Asian context, two recent studies on the Bank Islam Malaysia by Man (1988) and the Philippine Amana Bank by Mastura (1988) deserve special mention.

2.2.12. Growth and Profitability of Islamic Banking

The Malaysian experience in Islamic banking has been encouraging. Man's study shows that the average return to depositors has been quite competitive with that offered by conventional banks. Finally, in the most recent contribution to the growing Islamic banking literature, Nienhaus (1988) concludes that Islamic banking is viable. Nienhaus points out that there are some failures stories in which he has noted as troubles of individual banks that had specific causes and would be inappropriate to draw general conclusions from particular cases. Nienhaus notes that the high growth rates of the initial years have been falling off, but he rejects the thesis that the Islamic banks have reached their 'limits of growth' after filling market gap. But rather, the growth performance of Islamic banks has been relatively better in most cases than that of conventional banks in recent years. According to Nienhaus, the market shares of many Islamic banks have increased over time, notwithstanding with the deceleration in the growth of deposits.

2.3. Challenges Facing Islamic Banking Services

2.3.1. Lack of Awareness and understanding

Despite the growth of Islamic banking over the last 30 years, one of the main challenges facing Islamic banking is the poor understanding about its operations in the Muslim and non-Muslim world. (2005), Brown, Hassan and Skully (2007), Louis S. Nkwatoh et al. (2014)

2.3.2. Lack of Supportive Institutional and Market links

Islamic banking is at an early stage of learning and experience, lacking the flexibility to choose arrangements which best suits their need in reacting to structural shifts in the economic setting as well as changes in consumer preferences. For example, Islamic banks, without having an interest-free money and capital market, will not have adequate instruments to meet the pre-condition for liquidity management and effective maturity transformation. So, adequate financial mechanism still has to be developed, without which financial intermediation, especially the risk and maturity transformation, will not be performed properly.

Moreover, however well integrated it may be, any system cannot thrive exclusively on its built-in elements. It has to depend on a number of link institutions and Islamic banking is not an

exception to this rule. They also need research and training forums in order to promote entrepreneurship amongst their clients. Such support services properly oriented towards Islamic banking are yet to be developed in many countries.(Hassan and Skully, 2007).

2.3.3. The Regulatory Challenges

The relationship between Islamic banks and monetary authorities is a delicate one. Whatever the goals and functions are, Islamic banks came into existence in an environment where the laws, institutions training and attitude are set to serve an economy based on the principles of interest. For example, the operations of Islamic banks are on a profit and loss share basis (PLS), which actually does not come fully under the jurisdiction of the existing civil laws. In non-Muslim counties (i.e. countries with less than 50% Muslim population), central banks are very stringent in granting licenses for Islamic banks to operate. Islamic banks must also meet the additional requirements of other government and non-government authorities. (So, apart from legal constraints, there are economic measures that result operations of Islamic banks in non-Muslim world difficult).Momohet al (2011), the policy framework should provide the basis for competition of Islamic banks with conventionalbanks

2.3.4. Absence of Liquidity Instruments

Many Islamic banks lack liquidity instruments such as treasury bills and other marketable securities, which could be utilized either to cover liquidity shortages or to manage excess liquidity. This problem is aggravated since many Islamic banks work under operational procedures different from those of the central banks; the resulting non-compatibility prevents the central banks from controlling or giving support to Islamic banks if a liquidity gap should occur. Louis S. et al (2014).

2.3.5. Use of Advanced Technology and Media

Many Islamic banks do not have the diversity of products essential to satisfy the growing needs of their clients. The importance of using proper advanced technology in upgrading the acceptability of a product and diversifying its application cannot be over emphasized. Given the potentiality of advanced technology, Islamic banks must have to come to terms with rapid changes in technology, and redesign the management and decision-making structures and, above, all introduce modern technology in their operations.

Many Islamic banks also lack the necessary expertise and institutional capacity for Research and Development (R & D) that is not only necessary for the realization of their full potential, but also for its very survival in this age of fierce competition, sophisticated markets and an informed public. Islamic banking cannot but stagnate and wither without dynamic and ongoing programs. In addition, Islamic banks have so far not used the media appropriately. For example, even Muslims are not very much aware that the Islamic banking is being practiced in the world. Islamic banks have not ever used an effective media to publicize their activities, (Khan M and Bhatti, 2006) and (Mohammed, 2012).

2.3.6. Need for Professional Bankers

There is a need to institute professionalism in banking practice to enhance management capacity by competent bankers committed to their profession. Because, the professionals working in Islamic banking system have to face bigger challenge, they must have a better understanding of industry, technology and the management of the business venture. They also have to understand

the moral and religious implications of their investments with the business ventures. There is also a need for banking professionals to be properly trained in Islamic banking and finance. Most banks' professionals have been trained in conventional economics. They lack the requisite vision and conviction about the efficiency of the Islamic banking, Audu Bello et al. (2014).

2.3.7. Islamic Banking as a serious alternative Proposition

Despite skepticism regarding accommodation between Islamic and global finance, leading banks are forming subsidiaries specifically to conduct Islamic finance. Special laws have been enacted in non-Muslim financial centers to facilitate the operation of Islamic banks and associated financial institutions. Not so long ago, Islamic finance was superficially dubbed a zero-interest-rate system that would lead to inadequate and inefficient resource mobilization and utilization. Ironically, mainstream central bankers today routinely use precisely such policies when pursuing massive "quantitative easing."

Interestingly, the best economic rationale for a zero interest-rate system is provided in John Maynard Keynes "the General Theory" Keynes suggested that only a very low or zero interest rate could ensure continuous full employment and distributional equity. Keynes's endorsement of such a policy does not necessarily make it right, but his analysis does suggest that it should be regarded as a serious proposition. Islamic finance contrasts with the current dominant system based on interest-bearing debt, in which risks are theoretically transferred to debt holders, but in practice are socialized during crises. Other things being equal, most economists will agree that debt finance leads to greater instability than equity finance. It follows from the second major tenet of Islamic finance that if people adhered strictly to its ethical requirements, there would be fewer moral-hazard problems in Islamic banking. Moral hazard exists in all systems in which the state ultimately absorbs the risks of private citizens. But, whether any particular system is efficient in avoiding moral hazard is a matter of practice, rather than of theory.

Many would agree that, historically, Christian morality played an important role in the rise of Western capitalism. Secular capitalism however has experienced an erosion of values, whereby the financial sector has put its own interests above those of the rest of society. If the ethical values in Islamic finance – grounded in Sharia religious law – can further deter moral hazard and the abuse of fiduciary duties by financial institutions, Islamic finance could prove to be a serious alternative to current models of derivative finance. The test of any alternative financial system depends ultimately on whether it is – or can be – more efficient, ethical, stable, and adaptable than the prevailing system.

For now, there is no Islamic global reserve currency and no lender of last resort. But the Islamic world is the custodian of huge natural resources that back its trading and financial activities. As the Islamic world grows in stature and influence, Islamic finance will become formidable competitor to the current financial system. The world would have much to gain if the two systems were to compete fairly and constructively to meet people's needs for different types of finance, Ahmad A (2015), Development of the Islamic Banking System.

2.3.8. Islamic Finance in Ethiopia

Most of the developments of Islamic finance in the Ethiopia have taken place in the last eight years, but the existence of Sharia-compliant transactions in the Ethiopian financial industry

is yet something to be seen. A few banks began to offer simple products such Special Non-interest Savings Accounts (i.e. Special Demand Deposit offered by the commercial bank of Ethiopia (CBE)) to give a slight degree of choice flexibility to the Muslim Community before the current period. This did not, however, cater for the wider Muslim consumers. These products are relatively uncomplicated in structure and fell outside the scope of the mainstream consumers and did not generate significant volumes of customers and transactions, however, these compared unfavorably with their conventional equivalents in several respects, including their generally uncompetitive structure and negative real rate of return they offer. The growth of the Islamic Financial services remained stuck for almost half a decade since the first individual and group initiatives surfaced in early 2008. Much has not changed since then. Not a single commercial bank has announced yet that it will engage Islamic financial products whether publicly or privately owned, whether through ‘Special Window’ or subsidiary. Not a single „Full-fledged“ Islamic Financial Institution has come out still from so many publicized initiatives to establish what was dubbed as the first Islamic Financial Institution in Ethiopia. The current period not a single government initiative or program has still yet to come from the concerned authorities 756(2008 CBE).

Currently thanks to the **Ethiopian Prime Minister Dr Abiy Ahmed** During the Islamic holy month of Ramadan the Ethiopian Islamic community received miraculous news from the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE), the financial regulatory body, to resurrect the formation of Islamic Bank, the under formation of full-fledged interest free banking institution. In general this is a breakthrough for the Muslim community and also it is a good opportunity for the one who needs interest free banking system in particular. During a meeting held on May 22 /2011 E.C between the organizing committee members of Zemzem and Central Bank officials, Yinager Dessie, Governor of NBE, allowed Zemzem to undertake the formation process. The green light came on the same day that PM Dr. Abiy Ahmed, who, attended the massive Grand Iftar evening organized by the Ethiopian Islamic Affairs Supreme Council, announced that the government will allow interest free banking in the country.

Even though the case started immediately after the Banking Business Proclamation authorizing the establishment of interest-free banking in 2008, Zemzem was officially launched founding share sales in December 2010, and within a short period the organizing committee has been successfully amassed more than the proposed 250 million birr capital. Before the first general assembly held in April 2011 the actual collection was 330 million birr. Even though the under formation bank raised a significant amount of money within a few months and concluded the first general assembly effectively the pioneer on-conventional bank could not open a single door for operation because the NBE directive was ratified in September 2011, barring Islamic banking. The late directive to override the 2008 Banking Business Proclamation stated that Islamic banking operations are permissible only as part of other services and thus a fully Islamic bank was not allowed. The situation forced the then board of directors to call the first extraordinary meeting to disclose the situation to shareholders. On the occasion the board of directors of Zemzem told shareholders that the board held several discussions about the future of the bank before it called the extra ordinary assembly that was held on Saturday June 2, 2012. They said that in the past nine months the board members conducted several discussions with government and NBE officials to get an Islamic banking permit but to no avail. “We have also written a letter to the then the former PM to get solution on the issue but we did not get any response,” the board of directors explained. The board has clearly stated that the bank could not

continue in that situation and proposed three options for the shareholders; under Islamic banking injecting their capital on other banks and open a window, dissolving the bank and disburse back the raised capital or involve on other investment sector with the collected money, while shareholders preferred to get their funds.

But in the meeting most of the shareholders stated that, NBE's decision is against the country's constitution that allows citizens to involve in any business. "The central bank's decision is against our rights," the participants said. Nassir Dino, who is one of the organizing committee member and member of the first board of directors of the bank, remembered that for the last 12 months they have tried their best to realize the interest free banking, which is common not only in Islamic countries but all over the world. He said that since the late Prime Minister period "we have tried to convince the government about our mission.

We have also written a letter for the former PM but to no avail, but the one thing which is at least better is the Islamic banking scheme is operating in a separate window at conventional banks," he said. We have been working for our country as educated citizen not for sect, religious or group," Nassir recounts the motive of formation of such kind of financial sector, which is considered as best option on project financing since it focus on business idea than collateral as conventional banks. "The window has given hopes for us that one day the concept will get acceptance," he said. He further noted that the committee has written a letter to PM Abiy immediately after his assignment at his new post as PM. "We would like to appreciate the PM for taking quick action on the matter," he added. Sources said that last week the Deputy PM Office evaluated the case of Zamzam and they have called upon them to come up with a brief explanation about their case, while in the middle of this week the committee met with the governor and obtained permission. "The cost we lost is uncouncted compared with the harassment including the life threat we faced related to our activity," Nassir told Capital. He confirmed their meeting with the governor but declined to give further information about it. "In the coming weeks we will have concrete information regarding our future activity but for now we cannot talk details," he added. Experts in the financial industry and religious scholars claimed that the government previously misunderstood the concept of Islamic banking. Currently the interest free banking scheme is done at a separate window at ten banks, and over 30 billion birr has been mobilized. The President of Dashen Bank told Capital that initially the sector was not neglected since it is successful in other countries. "For instance other countries including neighbor states are practicing interest free banking but I don't know the reason why it is not allowed here, the central bank should answer that," the president explained. "We are currently working under a separate window by the support of Sharia advisory committee, which is like a board that follows the operation of interest free banking," he said. Experts said if the study was properly done and applied to the business it would be beneficial and would create a good opportunity for competition,(on June 2012,Capital and Fortune magazine).

2.3.9. The Need for Islamic Banking in Ethiopia

As horrendous disparities exist between different segments of the Ethiopian society, the government must provide the disadvantaged classes with the tools they need to improve their condition. Access to finance by the poor and the vulnerable groups is a prerequisite for poverty reduction and social cohesion. Such "financial apartheid" is one of the main causes of exclusion

of the majority of the population in terms of growth. Islamic banking is one way to ameliorate the poor and the disadvantaged segments of the society.

The Ethiopian banking sector has opened up considerably in the past decade or so and openness to interest-free banks is a logical next step. The potential benefits of allowing Islamic banking include; decreased economic disparity between the haves and the have notes, better integration, and consequently accelerated economic growth.

Government of Ethiopia can leap a step closer towards the fulfillment of the much cherished dream of "Middle Income Country" by reforming its banking sector and allowing the establishment of Islamic Banks. Islamic faith prohibits the use of financial instruments that pay interest. The no availability of interest-free banking products (where the return to the investor is tied to the bearing of risk) results in some Ethiopians, including those in the economically disadvantaged strata of the society, not being able to banking products and services due to reasons of faith. While interest-free banking is provided in a limited manner through SMFI, it's recommended that measures be taken to permit the delivery of interest-free finance on a larger commercial scale.

This is in consonance with the objectives of inclusion and growth through innovation. Also, it would be possible, through appropriate measures, to create a framework for such products without any adverse systemic risk impact.

2.3.10. Prospects and Opportunities for Islamic Banking in Ethiopia

The prospect of Islamic Banking looks very bright. Ethiopian Muslims everywhere want Islamic Banking. In addition, Ethiopia having more than 50 million Muslims offers huge opportunities to exploit. The size of the market will be very large as majority of Ethiopian Muslims, in the name of religious faith, are looking for interest free financial services.

It is pertinent to mention here that Islamic banking is not meant for Muslims only but non-Muslims may also avail the benefit of it. And it is feasible to have a parallel banking system: one based on Sharia along with a conventional one. The Growth and Transformation Plan, third five year economic plan, envisages inclusive growth with development in all sectors of the economy. Islamic banking is an effective mechanism to subjugate the liquidity and inflation problems while allowing inclusive growth. For real inclusive growth, which requires increase in income and employment should be ensured for all segments of the society. If Islamic banking is introduced, the inadequate labor capital ratio, for informal sector workers and farmers associated with agriculture and manufacturing industries could be resolved through equity finance, which might be a revolution in our agriculture and unorganized sector.

With improved labor capital ratio, our vulnerable workers associated with agriculture and unorganized sector might be able to compete effectively with the formal sector workers. Thus Islamic Banking may financially empower majority of Ethiopian workers and farmers. (Mohammed 2012)

Islamic banking may induce our political leaders to substitute grants and subsidies with equity finance which helps achieve self-reliability that never comes through grant and subsidies schemes, through specialized financial institutions. Moreover, with introduction of Islamic banking, Ethiopian government will certainly gain diplomatic advantages to make financial

dealings with Muslim dominated nations especially to attract trillion dollars of equity finance from the gulf countries. Finally, Islamic banking should not be regarded as religion based banking business, but could be profitably used to resolve issues pertaining to economy.

Prospects for Islamic banking although there are some problems, the prospects for Islamic banking seem to be higher and brighter in Ethiopia. The following factors suggest that the Islamic banking industry would grow very fast in Ethiopia. They are the positive attitude of the people, the support of the government of Ethiopia, the location of Ethiopia, the fact that Ethiopia is among the developing countries and the absence of banking facilities for the majority population in Ethiopia.

2.3.11. Positive attitude of the people

The people of Ethiopia, Muslims and non-Muslims, are very much interested to deal with Islamic banking. They know practically about the rigor of the riba based economic system. It is observed that a considerable number of customers are non-Muslims.

Non-Muslims are also interested studying in this field for job opportunities through which the message of Islam and knowledge of Islamic economics will be dispatched to the people of Ethiopia.

2.3.12. Support of the government of Ethiopia

Currently the Government of Ethiopia is supporting the Islamic banking system by making necessary amendments to the banking laws, which are crucial for the smooth running of the industry. However, it is anticipated that a few more amendments are yet to be made in the course of time. The government may continue to support and sustain the industry in the long-term.

A group consisting of bankers, Sharia scholars and industry players may be set up in the Central Bank Ethiopia and as the same time other commercial banks of Ethiopia, which will meet on a quarterly basis or as prescribed by the committee in order to discuss issues arising from the carrying out of the Islamic banking business. This will pave the way to take the necessary steps to resolve them promptly. This sort of committee is functioning in the UK Treasury with the same objectives spelled out above (Treasury Islamic Finance Expert Group, 2010).

2.3.13. Location of Ethiopia:

Ethiopia exists in an important location. With its ideal location in the East Africa, many natural resources existing in the country and its integration with many African and Asian countries, specially Arab countries.

2.3.14. Ethiopia is among the developing countries,

Being a developing country is a potential place to grow Islamic banking and likewise, the country can also benefit from this growth. Every branch of the country's system is to be developed. Highways, basic infrastructure, the alleviation of poverty, developing the agriculture, the establishment of new industries are but a few. The country can learn from other countries like Nigeria, Kenya and others which benefits significantly from this system of banking.

2.3.15. Absence of banking facilities for majority population especially in the rural areas.

The banking sector of Ethiopia is functioning on par with those of developed countries. Due to the technological developments, banks and other financial institutions are able to provide the banking and financial services to people in rural areas. However, the lack of motivation and commitment from the banks and other financial institutions is the key problem in this respect. The encouraging fact is that in Ethiopia there were a large number of populations which uses mobile telephone similarly; almost all banks have these technological facilities, which may tie up with those mobile providers to introduce the financial services to the rural population. This is the best way to enhance the rural economy of the country (Abeywi, 2009). Therefore; this indeed is a golden opportunity for Islamic banks to utilize the potential untapped market and potential customers in rural areas.

2.3.16. Status of Islamic Banking in Ethiopia

Currently the government of Ethiopia allows Islamic bank as a full-fledged interest free banking system as of June 2011/2019. During the Islamic holy month of Ramadan the Ethiopian Islamic community received miraculous news from the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE), the financial regulatory body, to resurrect the formation of Zemzem Bank, and another banks under formation of full-fledged interest free banking institution. This moment is a breakthrough for a significant number of Ethiopian Muslim communities.

Islamic banking is at an incipient or infant stage. The existing legal framework currently permits full-fledged Islamic Banking. A lot of amendments need to be carried out in the prevalent legal set up while appropriate models need to be selected and implemented to suit society's diverse financial needs. To accommodate Muslims, who are by Sharia– Islamic law – prohibited from taking or giving interest (riba), commercial banks are currently offering zero interest and forcefully transferred in to interest free banking. However, fully-fledged establishments of Islamic banks, which offers the owners of capital to share the profits made by the entrepreneur who comes up with investment projects, is an untapped concept for the local financial sector.

2.4. Empirical Evidences

2.4.1. Empirical Evidences General review

Abdulmajid et.al (2015) wrote about the efficiency in interest free banking and conventional: banking an international comparison investigates the efficiency of interest free banks and conventional banks using an output distance approach. They obtained measures of efficiency after allowing the environmental influences such as country microeconomic conditions accessibility of banking services and the bank type. The parameter estimates highlighted that interest free banking appears to be associated with higher input usage .Furthermore, by allowing for bank size and international differences in the underling inefficiency distributions, it demonstrated statically significant differences in inefficiency related to these factors even after controlling for specific environmental characteristics and interest free banking .Due to this interest free banks are found to have high returns to scale than conventional banks. While this suggests that interest free banks may benefit from increased scale, they emphasis and the results suggest that identifying and overcoming the factors that cause interest free banks to have relatively low potential output for a given input usage levels will be the key challenges for Islamic banking in the coming decades (Abdulmajid et.al,2015).

Ismaeil, et al. (2015) showed the recent development of insolvency of many conventional banks made by the Central Banks to initiate the acquisition of some banks while others were ordered to merge. This was a strong signal to seek for alternative banking system. However, the advocacy for the Islamic banking system as alternative to conventional banking system has been received with mixed feelings. He also posited that awareness, manpower, legal framework, societal belief, cash requirements were some of the challenges while economic growth, attraction of investors, and fostering of egalitarian society are the likely prospects for the establishment of the interest free banking. He concluded that interest free banking system hold a potential to transform all sectors of the economy with eradication of poverty, equitable distribution of income and employment opportunities in the country through effective mobilization and allocation of capital. Roddney Wilson, (2010) indicated that interest free banking finance has become increasingly significant in financial centers in the West, notably London, despite the regulatory hurdles presented by operating in a non-Muslim financial environment.

At the same time interest Western bankers, many of whom have sought to get involved in this growing industry, view free financing methods as a challenge and opportunity. In client driven societies, there is willingness by those in financial services to listen and learn from the experiences of interest free banks, which in the longer run may bring a major breakthrough for interest free banking at the retail level in the West.

Hanudin Amin, (2013) in his article of some view points of interest free banking retail deposit products in Malaysia indicated that those products were centered on the current accounts, saving accounts and investment accounts. These deposit products are examined in terms of their definitions, features and calculations. On the same note, some discrepancies between deposit facilities offered by interest free and conventional banks are exposed.

The purpose of such exposition was to provide to novice readers a basic but profound explanation concerning the difference between the two categories of deposit facilities.

2.4.2. Empirical Evidences in Ethiopian Context

In Ethiopia, IFB is a recent phenomenon. As a result, there is little empirical literature on the area. The studies conducted so far include the following: Among these studies Mohammed in2012 has studied the Prospects, Opportunities and Challenges of Islamic Banking in Ethiopia“ in his work discuss the potential challenges as: lack of awareness, regulatory, supervisory and institutional challenges, lack of support, gap in research and development in Islamic studies, lack of qualified human resource as well as wrongful association with specific religion and the global terrorism but This study was conducted before the practical introduction of the IFB in Ethiopia .Therefore, it was not based on actual observation of facts.

And also Akmel Hailu’s (2015) study is about “challenges and prospects of Islamic banking for resource mobilization in Ethiopian commercial banks. “The study focuses on challenges and opportunities of IFB only on resource mobilization other challenges and opportunities are not well addressed.

On the other hand are search by Debebe Alemu (2015) who studied the factors affecting customers' use of IFB in Ethiopia and found out that 100% of IFB account holders were all Muslims. Evidently, the failure of banks to meritoriously serve the Ethiopian Muslim population hinders the development of the Muslim inhabited areas in particular and the economy of the nation as a whole. This study is about impact assessment on the attitude towards IFB usage which does not address the current problem at hand. And also Teferi's (2015), study is about "Contribution of IFB to economic development and its prospect in Ethiopia". The contribution of the study includes assessing the Muslim population in to the banking (financial system) to the economic development and GDP growth.

This study has a gap of taking the realities of other countries and in Kerima Ali Mohammed's (2016) study which is about "Challenges on Interest Free Banking Services" The study discuss the challenge faced by service providers and users of IFB products and scope of service provided by Ethiopian banking through IFB including whether there is unmet demand of users, awareness of customers and capacity of bank .the study doesn't addressed the opportunities of interest free banking as a new business strategy in Ethiopia. This, study, therefore, attempts to fill the above research gap by investigating the challenge and opportunity of interest free banking from the service provider's view.

The purpose of this study is identifying the challenges, prospect and opportunities of interest free banking in Ethiopia by selecting banks which provide interest free banking service after licensed by NBE. In terms of the methodology the researcher will use qualitative method approach using interview and questioners for data collection, descriptive research design will be applied. To address the gap the researcher assed empirical evidence to find out the challenges and prospect of interest free banking in Ethiopia. Depending on the empirical evidence in Ethiopia the main challenges to IFB services are: lack of commitment of the bank, lack of Sharia advisor, lack of supportive regulatory directives , Problem related to Ethiopian Commodity Exchange (ECX) law, lack of capacity to deliver IFB product at full rage, lack of awareness of customer about IFB products, lack of trust and confidence of customers, inadequate marketing and promotion, double taxation, nature of IFB products, unavailability of IFB products in all of its branches and the IFB being delivered in a full-fledged basis.

CHAPTER THREE

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Owing to the fact that in Ethiopia there is a significant Muslim population and Islamic banking is touching upon the concept of religion, therefore, it is assumed that Islamic banking in Ethiopia will take lead in coming years and offset the concentration of conventional banking in Ethiopia. Since it is passing through transition phase therefore, Islamic banking is facing several challenges at one end, but also providing opportunities for development and investment in this area.

3.1. Research Design

The research tries to investigate the prospects, opportunities and challenges in introducing Islamic financial services institutions in Ethiopia specifically banking industry. To conduct this study and to realize the objectives of the study, descriptive research design of survey method which was observational in its nature was used due to its appropriateness. Both qualitative and

quantitative data were collected to examine the awareness of the respondents. In order to achieve the main objective of the study a descriptive and explanatory research design was used to gather as much information as possible to show the challenges and opportunities of Interest free banking service of Ethiopian commercial banks. According to Ghauri and Gironhaug, (2005), the basic difference between the three main classes of research designs is exploratory, descriptive and explanatory. The research can be exploratory when it deals with unknown problem, Descriptive when there is an awareness of the problem and explanatory when the problem is clearly defined.

3.2. Research Approach

For the purpose of this study the research approach under takes both quantitative and qualitative methods will be applied, in order to achieve the target objectives of the research and in order to find answers to those research questions, the researcher will also have used various instruments and materials a clearly defined plan of action.

3.3. Research methods

As indicated above the researcher use survey research method that satisfy the questions and the objectives raised by the study basically to identify and analysis the awareness' as well as the attitudes of the respondents both methods are appropriate. And also as a method the study use descriptive method by developing questions to the respondent's.

3.4. Research Techniques

The purpose of this study is to examine and analyze the prospect and opportunities of Islamic Banking in Ethiopia. For our Research study we have chosen qualitative method. In conducting qualitative research different methods are used namely, questionnaire, interview, case study, direct observation, role play and focus group. We have used primary and secondary method to obtain data on the subject. In primary research we have taken obtained input from professionals, Islamic bankers and Islamic banking clients. We have asked closed ended and open ended questions but in a structured way. Data for our primary researches are collected through two methods namely questionnaire and detailed interview. Research methodology is based on analysis. This research paper is based on primary data and secondary data collected through questionnaires among others; professionals were selected from West Addis District Commercial Banks from which currently opened full-fledged Islamic banks. The secondary data collected through documents, books, magazines and internet web-sites.

3.5. Sample Design

Sample design refers to the plans and methods to be followed in selecting sample from the target population and the estimation technique formula for computing the sample statistics. These statistics are the estimates used to infer the population parameters. Therefore, the researcher uses the sample design procedures that are target population, sample unit, sample frame, sample size determination and sample size.

3.5.1. Target Population

A population can be defined as all people or items (unit of analysis) with the characteristics that one wishes to study (Kothari, 2004). CBE has totally fifteen districts in Ethiopia based on location. Branches that are located Addis Ababa city are divided in to four districts which are North Addis, South Addis, West Addis and East Addis. To make the research manageable, West Addis district of the bank are considered in this research, which has the largest number of branches and also consist 4 special branches of the bank from those 5 branches based on their deposit and customer base. Besides, the number of branches offering IFB service stood at 100 with in this district as of December 2019. Since the study aim is to identify the challenges and prospect of interest free banking in CBE West Addis district, the target populations are the entire IFB –employees of the CBE in West Addis district and IFB customers of the district.

3.5.2. Sample Frame

A sampling frame is a list of the actual cases from which sample will be drawn. The sampling frame must be representative of the population. Therefore, from the study of this research the researcher determine the sample frame. The study population consists from West Addis district of Commercial Banks of Ethiopia.

3.5.3. Sampling unit

The target population that the researcher identify and the sample frame for the study which already explained in the research ; so that the sample units will be from the CBE IFB employees, West Addis District, number of sample branch, selected branch in the district, selection of customer from branch and selection of sample IFB staff.

3.5.4. Sample Techniques

The rationale behind the decision to use stratified sampling and simple random sampling system to select from each strata as well as the decision with regard to the sample size is that of simplicity, less time consuming, and of course, cost effectiveness. The research will apply multi-level sampling method in which the population is classified in to independent stratus in the first level by stratified random sampling. From each of them, respondents will be chosen using simple random sampling technique. For the purpose of understanding the CBE West Addis District and selection of sample IFB staff the researcher uses Purposive sampling and for selected branch in the district and selection of customer from branch will be simple random and convenient sampling techniques respectively.

3.5.5. Sample Size Determination

Determination of sample size is probably one of the most important phases in the sampling process. Generally the larger the sample size, the better is the estimation. But always larger sample sizes cannot be used in view of time and budget constraints. The target population of this study is the employees and customers of commercial banks in Ethiopia West Addis district. Due to resource constraint, it is difficult to cover all branches and to keep the study manageable; however, the study will focus on branches which are located in Addis Ababa. All branches have delegated employees who provide the service to their customers on the branch. A sample is a small proportion of a population selected for observation and analysis. The researcher used multistage sampling techniques to determine sample branch from the districts and of respondents-customer and staff.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-1: Sample Size Determination method
 Source: Adapted from Carvalho, 1984

Number of branches in Addis Ababa	51-90	91-150	151-280	281-500	501-1200	1201-3200	3201-10000	10001-35000	35001-150000
Small	5	8	13	20	32	50	80	125	200
Medium	13	20	32	50	80	125	200	315	500
Large	20	32	50	80	125	200	315	500	800

The researcher used simple random sampling. The study used a large sample size based on determination method developed by Carvalho (1984). Therefore, based on Carvalho sample size determination method the researcher has selected large sample size which is 22 branches of CBE with IFB in Addis Ababa West Addis District from the population of 50 bank's branches where in the larger number is considered to increase the accuracy of the data. After determining the appropriate number of sample branches from each district, simple random probability sampling technique which is lottery method is applied to select sample branch branches. The technique is applied because the fact that the technique is simple, unbiased and it provide customers and staff with an equal chance of being selected.

Customer sample size to determine the number of sample from the customer of the bank- a sampling technique called Small Sample Techniques from National Education Association formula has be used (Krejcie&Morgan 1970). The formula has been used by Debebe (2015), Teferi (2015) and Kerima(2016).The formula is:

$$S = \frac{X^2 NP (1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + X^2 P (1-P)}$$

WHERE S= required sample size, X²= Table value of X² for 1 degree of freedom as the designed confidence level (i.e. 3.8416), N= population size, P= population assumes to be (0.50 since this provide the maximum sample size), d= the degree of accuracy expressed at the proportion (0.05) Based on the above formula, from population of 26,901 IFB deposit customers sample size 456 of has been determined. Since the number of customers in each branch is not the same, the researcher used proportional computation to the number of customer in each selected branch. That is to determine the number of respondents in each branch, the proportion of each branch's customers in relation to the total number of customers considered. Thus, the number of respondents from the respective branch computed as follows:

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-2: Proportional distribution of questionnaire

Category(group)based branch	Total Number of customer	percentage from total population	Total number of customer sample
Betel TeqwaBranch	700	4.44%	20
AlembankMusab Branch	622	3.33%	15
Ayer tenaBranch	643	4.00%	18
GirarBranch	20	1.55%	7
KaraqoreBranch	598	4.67%	21
AlembankBranch	100	1.55%	7

Betel TeqwaBranch	600	4.88%	22
TotalBranch	390	2.88%	13
Mobil Posta BetBranch	475	3.77%	17
Kolfe 18 NOCBranch	372	2.88%	13
AtenateraBranch	406	3.33%	15
LukandaBranch	500	3.69%	16
MebrathailBranch	63	1.11%	5
EyesusGedamBranch	108	1.55%	7
Ayer Tena TesfaDirigtBranch	306	4.22%	19
Alembank TropicalBranch	462	3.77%	17
TorhailochBranch	481	3.77%	17
Betel TikurAbayBranch	300	2.67%	12
TikurAbayBranch	276	2.44%	11
WingateBranch	750	3.11%	14
ZenebwerkBranch	255	1.77%	8
KeraniyoBranch	282	2.88%	13
Weirasefer Branch	175	3.33%	15
Asko Branch	100	4.44%	20
Birchiqo Branch	300	2.89%	13
Aratmenta Branch	448	1.33%	6
EbadurehmanMesgid Branch	367	2.00%	9
Lomimeda Branch	388	2.67%	12
Aweliya Branch	200	3.55%	16
Sansusi Branch	231	2.88%	13
Tabotmaderiya Branch	250	3.58%	16
Total 3 qutirmazoriya Branch	400	2.22%	10
Mehandis Branch	300	2.90%	13
Total	10108	100	450

Source: own survey 2025

3.5.6. Types and sources of data

In conducting this study both primary and secondary data were used. The sources of primary data were employees, managers and personnel of the four banks affiliated with Islamic or IFB services. These data were collected by using a structured questionnaire which comprised information related with the respondents demographic characteristics, the information on the IFB services, on the prospect, challenges and on the opportunities of IFB systems.

Secondary data were also collected and used to describe and elaborate the conceptual aspects of the interest free banking and financing services and their applicability. Information was obtained from different websites, books written by various authors, bulletins released by foreign banks and by both the National bank and commercial banks of Ethiopia, thesis and papers were also consulted.

3.5.7. Data Analysis and Interpretations

The collected data were checked, sorted and screened for any errors. The researcher used quantitative data analysis techniques. To analyze the data descriptive statistics methods were used. Numerical data collected by close ended questions on the questionnaire were categorized and organized into tables and analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, mean scores and standard deviation. The results were then interpreted by writing descriptions about the quantitative data. The information collected from open-ended questions was analyzed using narrative technique.

The collected data was sorted and screened for any errors and then tallied to prepare tables for making analysis. Besides, the study attempts to analyses the various issues that evolve around prospects and challenges of Islamic banking in Ethiopia, such as misconceptions, awareness, legal and regulatory frame work, etc. The primary data was analyzed using the applicable statistical tools after all the necessary primary and secondary data are gathered and edited for any errors as well as omissions. The data was presented in a useful and organized manner suitable for analysis.

3.5.8. Data presentation

Data are a set of facts, and provide a partial picture of reality. Whether data are being collected with a certain purpose or collected data are being utilized, questions regarding what information the data are conveying, how the data can be used, and what must be done to include more useful information must constantly be kept in mind.

Data can be presented in one of the three ways:

- As text;
- In tabular form; or
- In graphical form.

Methods of presentation must be determined according to the data format, the method of analysis to be used, and the information to be emphasized. For the purpose of the study the researcher present the data by using tabular form and explained the table by a text presentation to clear and more understandable by the reader or users of this research.

3.5.9. Validity and reliability

Reliability and validity are concepts used to evaluate the quality of research. They indicate how well methods, technique or test measures something. Reliability is about the consistency of a measure, and validity is about the accuracy of a measure. It's important to consider reliability and validity when you are creating your research design, planning your methods, and writing up your results, especially in quantitative research.

Therefore, the researcher clearly identifies the validity and reliability of the research. The methods that the researcher used is that both quantitative and qualitative research approach for better description of the study.

Validity refers to how accurately a method measures what it is intended to measure. If research has high validity, which means it produces results that correspond to real properties, characteristics, and variations in the physical or social world. High reliability is one indicator that a measurement is valid. If a method is not reliable, it probably isn't valid. Due to this reason the researcher, methodology and sampling techniques are more reliable and valid. The researcher develops accurate sampling procedures.

The researcher uses the sources of the data both primary and secondary which was document review questions and personal interviews were used to gather data for the study. Research papers on Islamic banking, textbooks, magazines, and websites were used to analyze information for the purpose.

Questionnaire were prepared with the help of some banking experts and structured in a way that would enable everyone to answer and contribute something. The main source for secondary data is the Qur'an and hadith' narrations, unpublished project reports, data extracted from websites, CSA, IMF's Finance & Development Manuals, Academic Journals, texts and newspapers, etc.

3.5.10. Ethical Considerations

Ethical Considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. Thesis may even be doomed to failure if this part is missing. According to Bryman and Bell (2007) .The following ten points represents the most important principles related to ethical considerations in Thesis:

1. Research participants should not be subjected to harm in any ways whatsoever.
2. Respect for the dignity of research participants should be prioritized.
3. Full consent should be obtained from the participants prior to the study.
4. The protection of the privacy of research participants has to be ensured.
5. Adequate level of confidentiality of the research data should be ensured.
6. Anonymity of individuals and organizations' participating in the research has to be ensured.
7. Any deception or exaggeration about the aims and objectives of the research must be avoided.
8. Affiliations in any forms, sources of funding, as well as any possible conflicts of interests have to be declared. Any type of communication in relation to the research should be done with honesty and transparency.
9. Any type of misleading information, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided.

In order to address ethical considerations aspect of the study in an effective manner, the researcher will need to expand Voluntary participation of respondents in the research is important. Moreover, participants have rights to withdraw from the study at any stage if they wish to do so. Respondents should participate on the basis of informed consent. The researcher hope-fully informed providing sufficient information and assurances about taking part to allow individuals to understand the implications of participation and to reach a fully informed, considered and freely given decision about whether or not to do so, without the exercise of any pressure or coercion. Confidentiality of your information is kept and the results will be aggregated and presented only in summery form.

Ethical conduct states that it is the responsibility of the researcher to assess carefully the possibility of harm to research participants, and to the extent that it is possible, the possibility of

harm should be minimized (Bryman& Bell, 2007). During the data collection and interpretation processes, the researcher convinced the participants that any confidential information they disclose will keep confidential and convince them the important of the study is to help the bank and the employees. The respondents also informed, the exercise is only for academic purposes and that confidentially is assured and no one would fall a victim because of any adverse findings in connection with their professional duties. This is done in order to motivate them to give their responses without reservation. Every questionnaire attached to a cover letter which clearly explained the purpose of the survey. The questionnaire didn't require the names of the respondents; this was to protect their identity and remain anonymous. As a result, the employees are aware from the beginning what the researcher doing, why and where the information going and why it gathered.

CHAPTER FOUR

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Islamic banking in Ethiopia will be analyzed in the following sections of this in this chapter, the results of the study on prospects and challenges of Islamic Banking in Ethiopia will be presented. The data collected from participants and secondary sources about the awareness, general understanding, challenges as well as the need for chapter.

4.1. The Current Status of Islamic Banking in Ethiopia

In Ethiopia, most of the developments of Islamic finance have taken place in the last ten years and limited Sharia-compliant products are offered by few commercial banks like Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE), Somali Micro-finance Institution (SMFI) and NIB Bank. But, the existence of full set of Sharia-compliant transactions in the Ethiopian financial industry is yet something to be seen.

In Ethiopia, few banks began to offer simple financial products (i.e. the Special Demand Deposit offered by the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE) and the Amanah (or Safe and guarding) Account and the Micro-credit scheme (Murabaha) offered by the Somali Micro-finance Institution (SMFI)), to give a slight degree of choice and flexibility to the Muslim Community. However, the final directive issued by the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) has only allowed for the “Existing banks” to provide „interest-free banking windows” while killing the long awaited hope for full-fledged Islamic banking in Ethiopia.

4.2. Data Presentation

4.2.1. Respondent’s Demographic Variables

Respondents were asked to give their personal information and the results were presented in the following tables and sections.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-3: Respondents’ Demographic Variables based on Gender

Gender	Count	Table Total N %	Row N %
Male	298	66.2%	100.0%
Female	152	33.8%	100.0%
Subtotal	450	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2025

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-6: Respondents' Demographic Variables based on Gender

From the above figure the results showed that the majority of respondents were male (66.2%, N=298) while the rest were female that is 33.8%. Given the fact that the people who filled the questionnaires were expected to be the banks' employees who are affiliated with the IFB system, this implies that the majority of people with knowledge about IFB in the banks are males.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-4: Respondents' Demographic Variables based on age

Age	Count	Table Total N %	Row N %
21-30	299	66.4%	100.0%
31-40	128	28.4%	100.0%
41-50	20	4.4%	100.0%
51-60	3	0.7%	100.0%
Subtotal	450	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2025

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-7: Respondents' Demographic Variables based on age

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-5: Respondents' Demographic Variables based on level of education

level of education	Count	Table Total N %	Row N %
below 12 grade	51	11.3%	100.0%
12 grade complete	0	0.0%	0.0%
Certificate	8	1.8%	100.0%
Diploma	8	1.8%	100.0%
Degree	314	69.8%	100.0%
Master	69	15.3%	100.0%
Subtotal	450	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2025

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-8: Respondents' Demographic Variables based on Education level

With regard to the educational background of the respondents, from table 4-3, 51(11.3%) of them below 12 grade, the respondent 0(0%) 12 grade complete, 8 (1.8%) of the respondents have Certificate education level, 8 (1.8%) of the respondents have Diploma education, 314(69.8) of the respondents have degree while 69 (15.3%) of the respondents have some Master level education.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-6: Respondents' Demographic Variables based on religion

Religion	Count	Table Total N %	Row N %
Muslim	117	26%	100.0%
Orthodox	240	53.3%	100.0%
Protestant	93	20.7	100.0%
Subtotal	450	100%	100.0%

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2025

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-9: Respondents' Demographic Variables based on religion

The figure shows above religion of sample respondents was also among the characteristics examined to understand if there was a person who had an understanding of the Sharia principles and hence would provide a boost to the bank's IFB services. The results (See table 4.4) revealed that among the respondents who were all bank employees only 26 % (N=450) were Muslims, whereas the biggest proportion 53.3% were Orthodox Christian and the rest 20.7% were Protestant . This may imply that this service is being implemented by people who may not even have a clear understanding of what it stands for, unless special trainings have been delivered this could have effects on the implementation of this banking system.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-7: Respondents' Demographic Variables based on Educational level

level of education					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	below 12 grade	51	11.3	11.3	11.3
	Certificate	8	1.8	1.8	13.1
	Diploma	8	1.8	1.8	14.9
	Degree	314	69.8	69.8	84.7
	Master	69	15.3	15.3	100.0
	Total	450	100.0	100.0	

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2025

NB: respondents were excluded due to missing data

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-10: Level of education vs. Frequency

As table (4-1) indicated above, from the total sample of 450 respondents, 298 (66.2%) of the respondents were male and 152 (33.8%) of them were Female. Table (4-2) also shows the characteristics of the respondents. According to the data shown in the table (4-2), 299(66.4%) of the respondents fall in the age category between 21-30Years, 128 (28.4%) of them are in the age category between 31-40Years, 20(4.4%) and (0.7%) fall age category between 51-60Years.

With regard to the educational background of the respondents, from table 4-3, 51(11.3%) of them below 12 grade, the respondent 0(0%) 12 grade complete, 8 (1.8%) of the respondents have Certificate education level, 8 (1.8%) of the respondents have Diploma education, 314(69.8) of the respondents have degree while 69 (15.3%) of the respondents have some Master level education. Finally, from table 4-4, 117 (26%) of the respondents were Muslims, 240 (53.3%) of them were Orthodox Christians while 93(20.7%) of them were Protestants.

The study sought to determine the education level of the respondents from those involved in the study. From table 4-3 revealed that the majority of the respondents 69.8% of are university degree graduates, followed by those of masters holders with 15.3% and others 11.3% of the respondents are below 12 grades

4.2.2. Awareness, about Islamic banking

Awareness and general understanding is crucial if Islamic Banking is to thrive in Ethiopia. One of the research questions was ‘Is there low level of awareness and Understanding regarding the operations of Islamic banking and does it pose serious challenge to the success of Islamic banking in Ethiopia?’

4.2.2.1. Awareness about Islamic Banking Operations

Respondents were asked to answer certain items that will scale their assessment regarding Awareness about Islamic banking operations. The following table shows the results for respondents’ mean awareness score and their understanding about Islamic banking Operations. The result is showed on table (4-6) as below.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-8: Awareness Score of Respondents

Descriptive Statistics					
Statements	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Do you believe that awareness is a serious challenge for the operation of Islamic banking system?	450	1	5	3.63	1.208
Do you think that all the service know about IFB or Islamic banking system?	450	1	5	2.98	1.176
Do you think that the interest factors under conventional banking profit factor under Islamic banking system are two different concepts?	450	1	5	3.86	.966
Do you think that Islamic banking is the fastest growing financial sector globally because it has elements of fairness?	450	1	5	3.45	1.346
Do you know that interest is prohibited in all major religious scriptures and not only in the holly Qur'an?	450	1	5	3.35	1.340
Valid N (list wise)	450				

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2025

As depicted on table (4-6), the mean value for respondents awareness scores was found to be (3.86) with standard deviation of (0.99) while the minimum and the maximum scores were (1) and (5) respectively. However, the mean value (3.86) is less than the Expected average score of (46). This indicates that the respondents' awareness level regarding the operations of Islamic banking is low.

Thus, in general, respondents have been exhibiting low awareness and understanding regarding the operations of Islamic banking and finance.

This finding is actually consistent with what Islamic Banking literature has revealed about the operations of Islamic Banking elsewhere.

4.2.2.2. Challenges facing Islamic (interest free) banking

The other objective of this research was to identify the challenges that commercial bank of Ethiopia has faced while providing IFB products and also the challenges that customer has faced to utilize IFB products.

Thus, this was set as one of the research questions to sought answer for. Both customers and staffs- line and management- of the bank have been requested about the Challenges of IFB products/services that they have faced.

Table **Error! No text of specified style in document.-9: The Status of the respondents about the Major challenges of IFB**

Statements	strongly disagree		disagree		neutral		agree		strongly agree	
	Count	Row N (%)	Count	Row N (%)	Count	Row N (%)	Count	Row N (%)	Count	Row N (%)
do you think there is negative attitude of people regarding interest free banking (wrong association with religion)	67	14.9		26.0	76	16.9	149	33.1	41	9.1
do you think that there is no skilled manpower who run Islamic banking system	92	20.4	210	46.7	58	12.9	49	10.9	41	9.1
do you believe to start Islamic banking there is lack of potential customer	124	27.6	234	52.0	35	7.8	41	9.1	16	3.6
there is agap in research and development in interest free banking service and interest free finance modalities to fill the gap in qualified human resource	34	7.6%	76	16.9 %	92	20.4 %	232	51.6 %	16	3.6%

there is legal ,supervisory ,regulatory and institutional challenge	25	5.6%	127	28.2 %	101	22.4 %	148	32.9 %	49	10.9%
Total	450	100	100							

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2025

As result illustrated on the above table, concerning of challenge of respondent in wrong associations on religion due to interest based banking system 14.9% of the respondents were strongly disagree, while 33.1%of the respondent are agree while 16.9% of the respondent are neutral while 26% of the respondent are disagree and 9.1%of the respondent are strongly agree

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-10: Interest free banking has strong legal and institutional framework

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	disagree	16	3.6	3.6	3.6
	neutral	102	22.7	22.7	26.2
	agree	242	53.8	53.8	80.0
	strongly agree	90	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	450	100.0	100.0	

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2020

Do you believe that the current global trends in financial service will have positive manifestation on the future of Islamic banking in Ethiopia?

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-11:Positive effects from global financial trends on IFB(future of Islamic banking in Ethiopia)

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly disagree	8	1.8	1.8	1.8
disagree	60	13.3	13.3	15.1
neutral	61	13.6	13.6	28.7
agree	272	60.4	60.4	89.1
strongly agree	49	10.9	10.9	100.0
Total	450	100.0	100.0	

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2025

A statement to understand the position of respondents on the statement whether positive global financial trends would affect Islamic banking (IFB) in Ethiopia. These Global trends include for example technological advancements, economic growth in Ethiopia and in Muslim communities. The results revealed that 60.4% (N=450) and 10.9% of the respondents agree and strongly agree respectively with the statement. On the other side a considerable number of respondents (13.6%) did not provide their position on the issue. The average of the sample which is 2.55(SD=1.233) also shows that the tendency of the sample is shows towards agreeing with the statement. Have you ever a plan for business expansion and /or new investment opportunity to be financed by bank loan due to the fact that the interest based banking system does not encourage Muslim business community to consider all possible business and investment opportunity

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-12:IFB leads to business expansion and investment(Possible business opportunity)

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	9	2.0	2.0	2.0
strongly disagree	17	3.8	3.8	5.8
disagree	126	28.0	28.0	33.8
neutral	107	23.8	23.8	57.6
agree	142	31.6	31.6	89.1
strongly agree	49	10.9	10.9	100.0
Total	450	100.0	100.0	

Source: Own Computation from Primary Data Source, 2025

Asked whether they thought that IFB favored the expansion of business and investments, the majority of respondents 31.6% and 10.9% agreed and strongly agreed respectively. The average of the sample which stood at 3.1 (SD=1.231) itself shows that there is a tendency to agreeing with the statement by respondents. The qualitative interview on the challenges and prospect of IFB is analyzed by using narrative approach and presented below.

4.3. Prospect of IFB

- ✚ One of the most important prospects of Islamic Banking is the existence of potential customer of IFB financial service of the bank in Ethiopian, Muslims community. As Mohammed (2012) study show the non-availability of interest-free banking products Results, many Ethiopians, including those in the economically disadvantaged strata of Society, to be excluded from financial services due to reasons of their faith.
- ✚ Ethiopia is a developing country and needs huge investments. Investment framework is favorable in Ethiopia. Ethiopia’s legal framework, which is the best and it protects foreign investors. Also, the economies of neighboring Islamic countries have limited opportunities to invest their country. Ethiopia has abundant human resource and labor force too. Introduction of Sharia-compliant banking will bring more Arab petrodollars into the country.

4.4. Challenges of IFB

The main objective of this research was to identify the challenges and prospect that commercial bank of Ethiopia has faced while providing IFB products and also the challenges that customer has faced to utilize IFB products. The challenges to utilized IFB by customers are identified by the customers by using distributing questioners to sampled customer. But the challenges which hindered IFB products from being delivered are identified by using structured interview to the line manager of the bank and IFB department manager. Both IFB department manager and branch manager of the bank have been requested about the challenges of IFB products/services that they have faced. The researcher has summarized the identified challenges as follows.

✚ **Lack of awareness and understanding**

Availability of less number of customers is one of the obstacles and limits the bank to be the existed one. As the respondent of the officials show that some banks may not deliver the service even for one customer within the whole day because of unavailability of customer. As the response of the bank officials, customers did not have trust if the product is delivered by non-Muslim staff and customer also believed that the service which it is delivered by the bank based Sharia compliant IFB product and services. As the response of bank officials, customers believed that there is mixing of IFB and conventional banking transaction and the bank is not even committed to give truly IFB services this has eroded the customers' trust.

✚ **Challenges to utilize interest free banking**

Unavailability of IFB products/services in all of its branches as the response show customers are CBE does not provide IFB to its all branches. And the response also show customer complained on not providing the service in all branches of the bank these can be taken as challenges to utilize the products by the customer.

✚ **Lack of trust with in the bank**

The result of the respondent of the bank officials indicated that customer believed that IFB the service which is provided by the bank are not fully separated from the conventional banking system. Customers are not satisfied with window based IFB service of the bank. The majority of the respondent of the staff show that in some branches there is only one IFB customer service officer these create gap to deliver the service when IFB CSO staff is absent or in lunch time. Conventional window also deliver the service to the customer or customer will returned without getting the service. Mix of IFB and Conventional banking create complain within the service that the customer to utilize and keep separate book account.

Generally the major challenges to deliver and utilize interest free banking are regulatory challenge, lack awareness and understanding, Lack of Sharia advisor, Lack of supportive supervisory directive; undeveloped Islamic primary market and non-existence of secondary marker for Islamic product are some serious problems of to deliver Islamic or IFB within the bank.

CHAPTER FIVE

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. CONCLUSION

The objective of the study was to assess the challenges and prospect of interest free banking to utilize and deliver. Accordingly the study assessed the types of interest free banking products used by all commercial of Ethiopian banks. Moreover, the demand levels for IFB products other than those currently provided by the bank are assessed. The finding of the study particularly showed that the Current financial service trends in Ethiopian and large marketing opportunity of interest free banking have positive signs on the future of IFB service Islamic banking in Ethiopia. Even if there is potential customer Customers are satisfied with the existed Interest free banking products and there is no demand/ request for additional IFB deposit products from customers. In the utilization of IFB products, double taxation, non-provision of IFB products/services in all branches, the IFB being delivered in a Window model, lack of trust and confidence qualified human resource in Islamic banking are the major challenges.

According to the respondents even though long process approval of Sharia board for innovation of IFB products cannot be challenge for IFB development, there is lack of suitable Banking policies and comprehensive legal framework, lack of awareness, lack of equity market, lack qualified human resource in Islamic banking, lack of trust by the customer, unavailability of IFB products in all branches and Unequal Treatment of Debt and Equity and Double taxation are some major obstacles that to deliver and utilize the service. The current study examines the challenges and prospect of IFB in commercial bank of Ethiopia west Addis District. It gives hindsight for the staff and management of Commercial bank of Ethiopian towards Interest free banking challenges and prospect. The contribution of this study is vital as it has identified the major prospect for the development of IFB system and challenges deliver and customers to deliver and utilize IFB products. However, the study is bounded by both area coverage and problem addressed. Therefore, future studies can be conducted with wider scope and the effects of these challenges on the success of IFB.

5.2. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the research finding the following recommendation are provided in order to enhance prospect, the delivery and use of IFB products in Ethiopian banking market .

- ✚ Currently the Islamic banks are regulated by the same framework as that of conventional banks. Since the two banking systems work differently, many issues of Islamic banking cannot be settled by the existing policy. A compatible regulatory framework will create a path for Islamic banks to compete freely with conventional institutions. NBE also should consider giving IFB products in separate facility, at least in dedicated branches of the conventional bank, in order to improve attitude and increase IFB adoption.
- ✚ Most of the training given to the staff of banks is in line with the conventional banking system. Compared to conventional banking concepts, Islamic banking is a very new discipline and has distinct rules and principles. This implies for, a need of training in the procedures and principles of Islamic banking which would further accelerate the growth of the sector. The bank needs to adopt comprehensive and regular training on the IFB products and service for those staff who are engaged in providing the service.
- ✚ The bank should have aggressive promotion and marketing campaign about IFB products to create awareness on IFB products by particularly towards the target market (the Muslim

community) must be done consistently by using several promotional campaigns should be planned like poster, banner, media, and etc

Alongside awareness creation, bank has to build the trust and confidence of its customer by being transparent/disclose all its products, transaction and its IFB business activity to the public and confirm they are in line with Sharia. To support this action further the bank immediately has Sharia advisors. According to Pasha (2014) perception of Muslims that is the trust and confidence about the existing practice of IFB is truly of Sharia compliant and not a copy of the conventional banking with a banner of Sharia compliant is very important issue for IFB existence and success.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Glossary of Interest Free Banking and Finance

Allah: The Creator, an Administrative of the Universe; God

Amanah: Trust, with associated meanings of responsibility, truthfulness and sincerity. As an important secondary meaning, the term also identifies a contract where one party keeps another's funds. This is in fact the most widely understood and used application of the term, and has a long history of use in Islamic commercial law. Now a day's HSBC has maintained Amanah bank accounts.

Arbun: Down payment; a non-refundable deposit paid by the buyer to the seller upon finishing a contract of sale, with the condition that the contract will be completed during the prearranged period.

Gharar: (Uncertainty) is a sophisticated concept that covers certain types of insecurity or contingency in an agreement. The prohibition on gharar is often used as the grounds for criticism of conventional financial practices such as short selling, speculation and derivatives.

Halal: Any activity or transaction that is according to law and also permitted in Islam is known as Halal.

Haram: Any business or contract that is unlawful and also prohibited in Islam is known as Haram.

Islamic banking: Financial services that meet the requirements of the Sharia or Islamic law. While designed to meet the specific religious requirements of the Muslim customers, Islamic banking is not restricted to Muslims: both the financial services provider and the customer can be non-Muslim as well as Muslim.

Ijara:Ijara is a kind of lease; it allows the bank to earn profits by charging rentals on the assets leased to the customer. IjarawaIqtinah extends the concept to a hire purchase agreement.

Maysir:(Gambling) one of three fundamental prohibitions in Islamic finance. The prohibition on maysir is often used as the grounds for criticism of conventional financial practices such as assumption, traditional insurance and derivatives.

Mudharaba: is an investment partnership, whereby the investor (the Rub ul Mal) provides capital to another party (the Mudharib) in order to undertake an investment activity. While

profits are shared on a pre- agreed ratio, loss of investment is born by the investor only. The Mudharib loses its share of the expected income.

Mudharib: The mudharib is the entrepreneur or investment manager in a Mudharabah who invests the investors funds in a project or portfolio in exchange for a share of the profits.

Murabaha: Purchase and resale. Instead of lending out money, the capital provider purchases the desired commodity from a third party and resells it at a prearranged higher price to the capital user. By paying this higher price over installments, the capital user has successfully obtained credit without paying interest.

Musharakh: profit and loss sharing. It is a partnership where profits are shared as per as agreed ratio whereas the losses are shared in proportion to the investment of each partner.

Prophet: Hazrat Muhammad Mustafa (PBUH)

Quran: The Holy book of Muslims revealed on Hazrat Muhammad Mustafa (PBUH)

Qard: A Qard is a loan, free of interest. Bank use this arrangement for current accounts holders. In essence, it means that Current Account is a loan to the bank, which is used by the bank for investment and other purposes.

Riba: Interest, Usury. The legal concept extends beyond just interest but in simple terms Riba covers any return of money on money-whether the interest is fixed or floating, simple or compounded, and at whatever the rate. Riba is strictly prohibited in Islam.

Sharia: Islamic law as revealed in the Quran and through the example of Prophet Muhammad (PBUH). A Sha'riah compliant product meets the requirements of Islamic law. A Sharia board is the committee of Islamic scholars available to an Islamic financial institution for guidance and supervision in the development of sha'riah compliant products.

Sharia advisor: An independent professional, usually a classically trained Islamic legal scholar that advises an Islamic bank on the compliance of its products and services with the sha'riah, or Islamic law. While some Islamic banks consult individual Sha'riah advisor, most establish a committee of Sha'riah advisors.

Sharia Compliant: An act or activity that complies with the requirements of sha'riah or Islamic law.

Sukuk: Sukuk is the Arabic name for a financial certificate but can be seen as an Islamic equivalent of bond. However, fixed income, interest bearing bonds are not permitted in Islam, hence **Sukuk** are securities that comply with the Islamic law and its investment principles, which prohibits the charging, or paying of interest. Sukuk is a certificate of equal value representing entire shares in ownership of tangible assets and services or the assets of particular projects or investment activity. entire shares in ownership of tangible assets and services or the assets of particular projects or investment activity.

Sunnah: way of life of Prophet Hazrat Muhammad Mustafa (PBUH); They said about anything, they act anything is called as Sunnah.

Surah: Chapters of Quran; there are 540 Sura in Quran.

Takaful: Islamic insurance. Planned as charitable collective pool of funds based on the idea of mutual assistance, takaful schemes are designed to avoid the elements of traditional insurance (i.e., interest and gambling) that are challenging for Muslims.

Tawarruq: Reverse Murabaha. As used in personal financing, a customer with an actual need buys something on credit from bank on a deferred payment basis and then instantly resells it for cash to a third party. In this way, the customer can take cash without taking an interest-based loan.

Wakala:Wakala is an agency contract which generally includes in its terms a free for the skill of the agent.

Zakat: Zakat is one of the five pillars of Islam. It is obligatory for Muslims to pay their wealth to specified categories in society when their annual wealth exceeds a minimum level.

Source: www.islamic-bank.com
www.ubl.com.pk

Appendix 2: Data Collection Instruments LIUTEBM University School of Graduate Studies PhD in Accounting and Finance Questionnaires for Data Collection

Researcher: AbdlmegidAwel Chali
Contact Address: +251-912071483
Email: awelabdlmegid519@gmail.com

This questionnaire is designed to collect information on the state of Islamic banking (IFB) .The information gathered is meant to be used in a study that the researcher is covering under the topic, **Assessment of Islamic banking: Prospects, Challenges and Opportunities in Addis Ababa; West Addis District**. Any information gathered will be used only and only for academic purpose only. Therefore, you are cordially requested to give an accurate and honest response so that we can produce quality paper that will serve the interest of the Muslim community.

Thank you in advance for your time and honest response!

Instructions about the questionnaires

There is no need to write your name or any other personal identity

1. For multiple choice questions, mark or circle the answer of your choice
2. Put “✓”mark as per the questions required in the box or answer in the space provided

Part One Respondent Profile (GENERAL INFORMATION).

Fill in the blanks provided by putting a cross (X) which indicating your correct choice.

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Age (Years)
I. 21–30 III. 41-50
II. 31-40- IV. 51-60
3. Please indicate your level of education
I. below 12grade V. Degree
II. 12 grade complete VI. Masterand III.Certificate
IV. Diploma

4. Religion:

Muslim

Orthodox

Christian

Protestant

Part Two Instructions: Below are items which deal with respondents' awareness about the nature and operations of Islamic banking, and items that will rate respondents' score of prospects and challenges facing Islamic banking. The items included in this questionnaire are all closed-ended questions. The respondents will be instructed for a list of statements whether using the scale from 1 to 5 (Where 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree and 5 = Strongly Agree).

No.	Awareness items	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Neutral	Strongly Agree
1	Do you believe that awareness is a serious challenge for the operation of Islamic banking system?					
2	Do you think that all the service provider know about IFB or Islamic banking system?					
3	Do you think that the interest factor under conventional banking and profit factor under Islamic banking system are two different concepts?					
4	Do you think that Islamic banking is the fastest growing financial sector globally because it has elements of fairness?					
5	Do you know that interest is prohibited in all major religious scriptures and not only in the Holly Qur'an?					
6	Do you think that Islamic banking is „only-Muslim“ affair?					
7	Do you know that Islamic banking operates in non-Muslim majority like western countries that have a small number of Muslim community side-by-sides with their well-established conventional banking and has a significant number of Non-Muslim customers?					
8	Is there any financial Institution in Ethiopia that currently provides financial services that are in line with Islamic banking services?					
9	Do you believe that Islamic financial system proposes strong alternative system with profitable, well governed, transparent and sustainable institutions that would provide a successful and comparable set of financial products?					
10	Do you think that the notion Islamic banking is for only Muslim society while conventional bank is for others is true?					

B. Challenges Facing Islamic (Interest free) Banking

Next, there are listed of items which deal with respondents view on challenge and prospect of interest free Banking in banking industries. These items will explore respondent's assessment of challenges facing Interest free banking. So Please tick the number that you feel most appropriate, using the scale from 1 to 5 (Where 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree and 5 = Strongly Agree).

No.	Items	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
	Do you think there is Negative attitude of people regarding Interest free banking (wrong association with religion)?					
	Do you think that there is no skilled manpower who run Islamic Banking system					
3.	Do you believe to start Islamic Banking there is lack of potential customers					
	There is a gap in research and development in interest free banking services and interest free Finance modalities to fill the gap in qualified human resource.					
	There is Legal, Supervisory, regulatory and Institutional challenge.					
	There is Lack of suitable banking policies for Interest free banking.					
	Interest free banking should be governed by Different set of regulations as they differ from conventional banks in many aspects such as risk structure, form of ownership and governance.					
	There is Lack of Trained Human Resource in Interest free banking.					
	The current commercial banks customers are fully satisfied with the range of products that the banks provide.					
	Interest free banking has strong legal and institutional framework.					

B. Prospects and Opportunities of Islamic (Interest Free) banking

No.	Items	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
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		Disagree				
1.	Do you believe that the current global trends in Financial Services will have positive manifestations on the future of Islamic banking in Ethiopia?					
2.	Have you ever cancelled (or would cancel) a plan for business expansion and/or new investment opportunity to be financed by bank loan due to the fact that the interest based banking system does not encourage Muslim business community to consider call possible business and investment opportunities?					
3.	Do you think there is a need for Islamic banking in Ethiopia so that it will alleviate the financial services deprivation of the Muslim community?					
4.	Do you think that, if the existing banks offer certain Islamic products (Saving and Loan Service), the access to Islamic banking will improve and the tendency for business expansion					
5.	Do you believe the current commercial banks, public or private, will engage in Islamic banking services that will address the Muslim community's need for Islamic banking services anytime soon?					
6.	If you are banking services user currently, do you think that Safety keeping money safe is your first priority?					
7.	Do you think that the likely reason(s) that many Muslims are not using banking services currently is due to the fact that 'Savings and loan services involve interest?					
8.	Do you think that people would use investment loan service due to its attractiveness and ease access?					
9.	Do you think that the „high prohibitive interest rates“ that conventional banks charge is the main reason that loan services are not currently widely used?					

1. What is the overall demand level for Islamic or interest free banking product other than those currently provided?
 - i. Satisfactory
 - ii. Not satisfactory
 - iii. I have no idea
2. What are the overall challenges which the bank faces in delivering Islamic or interest free banking? _____
3. What are the overall challenges which the customer faces in receiving Islamic or interest free banking? _____
4. What is the level of customer awareness on over all using of Islamic (Interest free) banking system? _____